

**POST GRADUATE
WORK EXPERIENCE REPORT**

BY

(Adeola Oluwaseyi ADELUWOYE)

**SUBMITTED TO
COUNCIL FOR THE REGULATION OF
ENGINEERING IN NIGERIA
(COREN)**

**FEDERAL REPUBLIC OF NIGERIA
COUNCIL FOR THE REGULATION OF
ENGINEERING IN NIGERIA**

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BY

(Adeola Oluwaseyi ADELUWOYE)

**SUBMITTED IN PARTIAL FULFILMENT OF THE
REQUIREMENTS FOR REGISTRATION AS AN
ENGINEER**

(CIVIL ENGINEERING)

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27th August, 2024

CERTIFICATION

I certify that this report was written by me and it is a record of my post-graduate work experience.

Adeola O. ADELUWOYE

Name

A.O.A August 2024

Signature and Date

I, the undersigned, have gone through the report that has been prepared and I endorse the experience attained and reported by the writer. Based on my personal knowledge of the character and professional reputation of the applicant, I recommend for acceptance of this work Experience report by the COREN in partial fulfillment of the requirements for registration as Registered Engineer.

Arinze D. Nnaekezie

Name

A.D.N August 2024

Stamp and Date

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CHAPTER ONE

1.0 INTRODUCTION

I am a graduate of the prestigious Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA) situated in the south-western part of Nigeria (Akure, Ondo State). I obtained a Bachelors of Engineering (B.Eng) in Civil Engineering in the year 2019 with a first class honours (CGPA 4.68/5.00) & and as the best graduating student in the Civil Engineering department, School of Engineering & Engineering Technology, FUTA. My undergraduate studentship equipped me with fundamental knowledge in Engineering Mathematics, Structural engineering; Geotechnical Engineering; Water and Waste Water Engineering, Highway Engineering. I served as a student academic tutor in the department of civil engineering, FUTA, during my 5 years academic journey from (2014 – 2019).

During my undergraduate studies, I was opportune to have my 6 months industrial training (I.T) in Planet Projects Limited situated in Lagos State, Nigeria in the year 2018. I was an on-site intern at one of our mega projects titled ‘Oshodi Bus Terminal’, the largest bus terminal in Nigeria. I had practical hands-on-the-job experience on rigid pavement construction, construction of foundation: strip, pad, pile-caps and piles, handling of dumpy level to affix spot elevations and setting out of pegs, construction methodology of composite floors for her pedestrian bridge.

Furthermore, my post-graduation experience from December 2019 till date have been filled with a robust expertise in the field of structural engineering covering analysis and design of reinforced concrete and steel structures. I have worked as a site structural engineer in Raycon Engineering Ltd; Structural design engineer in Integrated Advanced Analyst (IAA); and I currently work in Arup, Nigeria, as a structural design engineer in her structures department. I am proficient in the following software packages: Tekla Structural Designer; Autodesk Robot, CSC Tedds, Autodesk Revit structure and AutoCAD.

At Arup, Nigeria, I currently serve as her key structural design engineer who takes design classes using Tekla Structural Designer on reinforced concrete and steel structures. In addition, I have successfully designed several high-rise buildings, steel structures and outdoor structures such as a cenotaph.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 SUMMARY OF WORK EXPERIENCE

Period	Detail of Projects/Activities	Duration (Months)	Supervisor	
			Name	Signature
Pre-Graduation	<p>Employer: School of Engineering & Engineering Technology, Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA), Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Trainee</p> <p>Project: Student Work Experience Program (SWEP)</p> <p>Activities undertaken were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Technical report writing workshop. (ii) Construction of a 4 in 1 extension box. (iii) Visit to School of Engineering central workshop. (iv) Compressive strength test on concrete cubes (150mm x 150mm x 150mm) 	June–August (2017)	Professor O.O Ojuri	Head of Department, Civil Engineering, FUTA
Pre-Graduation	<p>Employer: Planet Projects Ltd</p> <p>Position: Trainee</p> <p>Project: Oshodi Bus Terminal, Oshodi, Lagos State, Nigeria</p> <p>Activities Undertaken were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Documentation of daily site activities for Terminal 3 bus station construction. (ii) Supervision of rigid pavement works for BRT carparks. (iii) Taking of daily site photographs to aid report writing for site engineers. (iv) Vetting of formwork alignment, and reinforcement positioning in accordance to detailed drawings. (v) Interpretation of RC details and issuance of instructions to site labourers. (vi) Inspection of construction works for composite floor. 	Feb – October (2018)	Engineer Chima Balogun	Senior Engineer

Post-Graduation	<p>Employer: Raycon & Co Nigeria, Ltd</p> <p>Position : Graduate Site Engineer</p> <p>Project: Calabar Free Trade Zone (FTZ)</p> <p>Activities undertaken were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Supervised the construction of counterfort retaining walls alongside a 2km flexible pavement. (ii) Prepared instruction module for the stone pitching of a 5,000m² slope to forestall erosion. (iii) Supervised the construction of drainage channels and culverts in Calabar Free Trade Zone (FTZ) annex. (iv) Quality assessment checks on spacing of rebars, placement of concrete covers, binding wires and formworks before casting of RC structures. (v) Reported daily site progress to the overall Resident site engineer. 	February, 2020 – March, 2021	Engineer Tijani	Senior Resident Engineer
Post-Graduation	<p>Employer: Integrated Advanced Analyst (IAA)</p> <p>Position : Graduate Structural Engineer</p> <p>Project: Four Seasons Hotel, Ikoyi, Lagos, State; Smokin Hill Hotel resorts, Ondo State.</p> <p>Activities undertaken were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Generated 3D structural models using Autodesk revit structures. (ii) Analysis and design of structural columns, beams, slabs and walls using autodesk robot structural analysis professional. (iii) Generated sections from architectural revit model to aid RC detailing works of technicians handling RC beams, walls, slabs and column details. (iv) Provided spot elevations throughout the coordination phases of the projects in order to enhance coordination between structural engineering team and MEP team. 	June 2021 - Feb 2022	Dr Adeleke Akintilo Engr Wale Adeosun	Principal Partner Associate

Post-Graduation	<p>Employer: Ove Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Graduate structural engineer/Project Engineer</p> <p>Projects:</p> <p>1. Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos state</p> <p>Activities undertaken were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Generation of site instructions for ongoing construction works on site. (ii) Overall 3D model, analysis and design of the 29 floor twin tower. (iii) Wind simulation and drift check on the entire model structure. (iv) Design of the front and rear steel canopy structures at the entrance and rare sides of the building. Design of its steel connections. (v) Carrying out of optimization of structural columns based on its axial loads and moment across each column stack. (vi) Generation of structural details for reinforced concrete structures: Beams, Columns, walls and slabs. (vii) Cross checking and marking up of structural detail drawings. 	March 2022 – Date	<p>Engr Emeka Okide</p> <p>Engr Tunji Fashanu</p> <p>Engr Arinze Nnaekezie</p>	<p>Deputy Chairman, Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Associate Director, Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Project Manager</p>
	<p>Employer: Ove Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Graduate structural engineer/ Project Engineer</p> <p>2. Projects: Mike Adenuga V-Towers, Victoria Island, Lagos</p> <p>Activities carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Attending online coordination meetings with architects and MEP specialist. (ii) Design of composite floor. (iii) Structural modeling of the entire 40-storey tower using Tekla Structural designer. (iv) Wind analysis 	December 2022 - Date	<p>Engr Tunji Fashanu</p> <p>Engineer Arinze Nnaekezie</p>	<p>Associate Director</p> <p>Project Manager</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> (v) Design of transfer columns, transfer beams, Structural walls, and slabs. (vi) Optimization of Reinforced concrete details and geometry of 			
Post-Graduation	<p>Employer: Ove Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Structural engineer/ Project Engineer</p> <p>3. Project: Proposed Steel Platform design, Nigerian Brewery, Ibadan</p> <p>Activities carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) 3D model of the 1-storey steel platform using Tekla Structural Designer (ii) Analysis and design of structural steel elements: stanchions, beams and braces using Tekla structural designer (iii) Design of suitable pad bases for the stanchions at foundation level. (iv) Coordination/ collaboration with architects and structural detailers during design phase. 	Jan 2023- April 2024	Engr Adeshina Bello	Principal Engineer
	<p>Employer: Ove Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Structural engineer/ Project Engineer</p> <p>4. Project: Proposed 5-Star hotel, Eko Atlantic, Lagos</p> <p>Activities carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Scheming of structural columns and beams for the 21-storey hotel. (ii) Scheming and design of structural steel roof. (iii) Design of structural columns, reinforced concrete shear walls, beams and slabs. (iv) Optimization of column sizes. (v) Telescoping of reinforcement quantities through stacks of column. 	Nov 2023 – Date	<p>Engineer Tunji Fashanu</p> <p>Engineer Arinze Nnaekezie</p>	<p>Associate Director</p> <p>Project Manager</p>

Post-Graduation	<p>Employer: Ove Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Structural engineer/ Project Engineer</p> <p>5. Project: EMOWAA archaeological centre</p> <p>Activities carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (vi) Scheming of structural columns and beams for the archaeological centre. (vii) Scheming and design of foundation (viii) Design of structural columns, reinforced concrete shear walls, beams and slabs. (ix) Optimization of column sizes. 	Jan – June 2023	Engineer Tunji Fashanu	Associate Director
	<p>Employer: Ove Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Structural engineer/ Project Engineer</p> <p>6. Project: Anglican Centenary Diocese, Lekki, Lagos state – Cenotaph</p> <p>Activities carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Schemed the position of reinforced concrete beams, columns, slabs and walls in accordance with the architectural footprint. (ii) Generated a 3D structural model for analysis and design using Tekla Structural designer and Autodesk Robot structural Analysis Professional. (iii) Wind Analysis on the Cenotaph. (iv) Generation of 3D structural model using Autodesk Revit structure. (v) Annotation of structural elements. (vi) Generation of sections, elevations, and 3D views of the Cenotaph structure. 	April- June 2024	Engineer Arinze Nnaekezie	Project Manager

Post-Graduation	<p>Employer: Ove Arup, Nigeria</p> <p>Position: Structural engineer/ Project Engineer</p> <p>7. Project: Anglican Centenary Diocese, Lekki, Lagos state – Steel Observatory Tower</p> <p>Activities carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Scheming of structural steel elements: stanchions, beams, braces, steel staircases. (ii) Design of structural steel stanchions, beams and braces. (iii) Design of pad foundations using Tekla Structural Designer. (iv) Wind analysis. 	May 2024 - Date	Engineer Arinze Nnaekezie	Project Manager
Post-Graduation	<p>Employer: Mountain of Fire & Miracles Ministries</p> <p>Position: Structural Design Engineer</p> <p>8. Project: Proposed Mountain of Fire Campus Fellowship building, Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA)</p> <p>Activities carried out:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> (i) Project coordination with the principal architect on the project. (ii) Scheming of structural columns to bear the gallery floor level of the structure. (iii) 3D model, analysis and design of structural elements supporting the church auditorium (iv) Design of staircases (v) Design of steel roof truss system to span the 25m clear span of the church auditorium (vi) Design of foundation (pad footings) 	August 2023 - Date (contract appointment)	Alumni Committee	Alumni Committee

CHAPTER THREE

3.0 DETAILS OF ENGINEERING WORK EXPERIENCE

3.1 Project

Proposed design of Mountain of Fire & Miracles Campus Fellowship, Auditorium, Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA), Akure, Ondo State, Nigeria

3.1.1 Project Particulars

Client: Mountain of Fire & Miracles Campus Fellowship, FUTA

Project cost: 320 million

Consultant: BUIENG IDEAS

Position held: Structural Design Engineer

Period: 8 Months

3.1.2 Project description

The client, Mountain of Fire & Miracles Campus Fellowship, has secured a convenient space estimated at 1,500m² situated at the out skirt of the North gate area of the Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA). The proposed building is to serve as her church building having a capacity of 1,000 sitting spaces for her congregants. The structure has a ground floor level and a suspended gallery floor level, where the rare side of the building will serve as a secretariat/ residential spaces for her executives presiding over the activities of the church. The roof portion of the building is composed of steel trusses spanning a clear space of 25m. The building is supported by reinforced concrete columns, beams, and 175mm thick solid slab system. The foundation type chosen is isolated pad footing to transfer the weight of the building unto the solid strata of the earth at a 1500mm depth.

Floor Level	Purpose
Ground Floor	Auditorium, pulpit area, President's office, store room, conference room, Ushering Unit office, Choir office, living area, sound system office, and lobby
1 st floor	Gallery, library, lobby, tutorial room, and living area
Roof	Steel roof trusses, purlins & aluminum sheet

Figure 1: Architecture external 3D rendering of proposed MFM campus fellowship

Figure 2: Architecture 3D internal rendering of the proposed MFM campus fellowship

Figure 3: 3D structural model of the proposed MFM campus fellowship

Figure 4: Applied loads on 3D structural model of the proposed MFM campus fellowship

3.3.3 Objective

The objective of the project were to model, analyze and design the church auditorium with a view to ensuring its stability & functionality, preserve its aesthetics, and ensure it is economical.

3.3.4 Scope of the work

- Specification of the grade of structural materials (concrete and steel).
- Scheming of structural columns and beams into the architectural layout
- Analysis and design of the structure to ensure its robustness and stability.
- Coordination with architect to ensure structural decisions aligns with aesthetics.
- Generation of structural detail drawings and annotations for structural elements.
- Design of isolated pad footings: sizes and reinforcements.

3.3.5 Software package used

- Tekla Structural Designer (TSD)
- AutoCAD
- Tekla Tedds for Element Design.
- Autodesk Revit Structure
- Reinforced Concrete Design Spread Sheets.

3.3.6 Applicable design standards and specifications

Category	Design codes	Descriptions
Loadings	BS 6399: Part 1 1996	Code of practice for dead and imposed loads
	BS 6399: Part 2 1997	Code of practice for wind loads
	BS 6399: Part 3 1988	Code of practice for imposed roof loads
Concrete	BS 8110: Part 1 1997	Code of practice for design & construction
	BS 8110: Part 3	Design charts for singly reinforced beams, doubly reinforced beams and rectangular column
	BS 8004:1986	Code of practice for foundations
Steel	BS 5950: Part 1 2000	Structural use of steel works in buildings
	BS 5950: Part 2 2000	Specification for materials, fabrication & erection
	BS 5950: Part 3 2000	Design in composite construction

Vertical limit of Deflection	
Total deflection under dead and imposed load	Span/250
Deflection under live loads	Span/360
Beams carrying plaster or brittle finish	Span/360
Other beams (except purlins and sheeting)	Span/200
Cantilevers	Span/180
Purlins and sheeting rails	To suit cladding

3.3.7 My involvement in the project

I worked as the project design engineer and carried out the following activities on the project:

- i. Prepared the General Arrangement (G.A) drawing for the project: schemed the positions of structural columns, beams, and load bearing walls in the structural layout.
- ii. Performed structural modeling, application of structural loads (dead: partitions, finishes, and services; imposed loads), analysis and of the structure using Tekla Structural Designer software.
- iii. Designed the structural columns, staircases, beams, slabs and isolated pad foundation to bear the weight of the structure and transfer the load to the earth.
- iv. Generated design calculation reports for the project
- v. Generated reinforcement details for reinforced concrete elements.
- vi. Coordinated with the architect on the progressive design phases and agreement on sizes and positions of structural elements in the project.

3.3.8 Challenges encountered during the course of the project

- i. The choice of Revit software in terms of version posed a challenge at first. The architect was using a higher version of Revit (Revit 2024), while I had Revit 2023 installed on my workstation. This made it difficult to access the architecture Revit model.
- ii. The gallery area of the building required raking/ inclined beams. This caused a lot of back and forth in terms of coordination.
- iii. Restriction on column placement in the main auditorium area.

3.3.9 Solutions proffered to the challenges encountered

- i. I had to install Revit 2024 in order to have access to the architectural file which was in Revit 2024. This led to effective coordination with the architect and easy information exchange.
- ii. Designed a 450mm circular column to support the raking/slanted beam of 300 width x 750mm depth in the gallery area. The choice of circular columns instead of square columns was to ensure aesthetics on the footprint of the ground floor and to aid visibility of congregant in the auditorium area.
- iii. Due to the restriction on column sizing due to the functionality of the structure. I designed all the perimeter columns to have same 230mm width with the block-wall so it does not bulge out of the wall. This is to preserve the aesthetics and finished look of the structure after completion.

3.3.10 Experience gained

- i. Improved skillset in using Autodesk Revit structure. I gained handful experience in superimposing my structural columns and beams on the architectural layout and seeing the impact on aesthetics and mobility. Hence making optima decisions that does not undermine the aesthetics of the structure.
- ii. Increased understanding of the analytical performance of structural elements under deformations and stresses. The graphical interaction of Tekla Structural Designer made it easy to see the analytical behavior of each structural elements via her animation capacity when viewing analytical results for members.
- iii. Improved knowledge on annotation of structural layouts using Autodesk Revit Structure. This involves marking up drawings for easy coordination and observation of revisions made by the architect.
- iv. Ability to generate structural details using Tekla Structural Designer to generate reinforcement details of structural elements as it was modeled, analyzed and designed.
- v. Improved skillset in generating structural calculation reports and overall document control to convey apt professional information.
- vi. Acquisition of foundation design knowledge and the importance of grouping foundation into significant sizes and quantities to aid easy and speedy construction works.

3.2 Project

Front Canopy, Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos State, Nigeria

3.2.1 Project Particulars

Client: Quantum Luxury Properties LTD

Project cost: 40 million

Consultant/ Structural Engineer: Ove Arup & Partners Nigeria LTD

Position held: Project Design Engineer

Period: 5 months

3.2.2 Project Description

The client, Quantum Luxury Properties LTD, one of the top 5% professionals in property development in the Island region of Lagos State, Nigeria requested the consultancy expertise of Arup, Nigeria in designing her front entrance steel canopy. The canopy has a length of 11m and a width of 7.2m. It is supported by Reinforced concrete columns on the rear side and on the front-side with a Y-shaped Circular Hollow Sections -CHS (Upper sides: 219.1 x 6.3 and lower side: 244.5 x 6.3). The roof-top of the canopy comprises of Square Hollow Sections – SHS (250 x 250 x 8) spaced equally at 1.2m and overlaid with a 50mm lightweight concrete top filling.

Figure 5: 3D Revit structural model of the front canopy, Metropolitan Tower

Figure 6: 3D architectural rendering of the front canopy, Metropolitan Tower

Figure 7: Plan view of the front canopy

Figure 8: Front view of the front canopy

3.2.3 Objective

To design the steel canopy with a view to ensuring its stability, safety and durability during its service life.

3.2.4 Scope of the work

- Specification of the grade of structural materials (steel and concrete).
- Scheming of structural steel into the architectural layout
- Modeling, analysis and design of the steel canopy to ensure its robustness and stability.
- Optimization of steel sections to achieve a cost effective design
- Design of connection for steel beams (SHS) to concrete beams, stanchion to base (ground floor slab), anchor bolts, base plate, bolts, and welds for steel joints.

3.2.5 Software packages used

- Autodesk Robot Structural Analysis Professional
- Autodesk Revit Structure
- AutoCAD
- Tekla Tedds

3.2.6 My involvement in the project

I worked as the project design engineer and carried out the following activities on the project:

- i. Prepared the General Arrangement (G.A) drawing for the steel canopy: schemed the positions of structural steel beams, and steel stanchions.
- ii. Performed structural modeling, application of structural loads (dead: 50mm structural slab topping, finishes, and services; imposed loads), analysis and of the structure using Autodesk Robot Structural Analysis Professional
- iii. Designed the steel connections using Tekla Tedds based on the shear force and bending moment values obtained from the analytical results from Autodesk Robot. Determined the sizes of the base plates, anchor bolts and specification of weld to be adopted for welding works where it is required.
- iv. Generated design calculation reports for the project.

3.2.7 Challenges encountered during the course of the project

- i. The architect wanted the entire 11m length of the steel canopy to cantilever from the supporting reinforced concrete columns. This posed a great challenge that led to the back-and-forth coordination of the support system of the lengthy canopy platform.
- ii. The large span of the canopy posed limits on the choice of steel sections that can be adopted. Hence, sections such as Universal beams (U.B) could not be adopted due to its susceptibility to buckling.
- iii. The thickness of the reinforced concrete beam (230 width x 900 depth) mm supporting the arrays of secondary beams (Square Hollow Sections – SHS 250 x 250 x 8) limited the type of anchor bolts that can be used. A normal J-ended bolt could not be used since 230mm thickness of beam was the limit permitted by the architect.

3.2.8 Solutions proffered to the challenges encountered

- i. A Circular Hollow Section (CHS) with a Y-shaped geometry was adopted to curb the 11m cantilevering length of the steel canopy at the front face. This enabled an economical choice of steel sections for the steel beams and effective control of moment as well.
- ii. Square Hollow Sections – SHS 250 x 250 x 8 was adopted instead of Universal Beams (U.B) which are susceptible to buckling considering the 11m span.
- iii. A Fischer ended anchor bolt was used as against the conventional J-ended anchor bolts. Thereby allowing for an embedment depth of 180mm into the 230mm thick reinforced concrete beam.

3.2.9 Experience gained

- i. Detailed understanding of the concept of lateral torsional buckling as it relates to steel beams. Considering the choice of a Square Hollow Section over Universal Beams.
- ii. Professional and theoretical knowledge on the design of connections which consisted of the usage of Tekla Tedds software and consultations using a textbook titled ‘Design of structural elements by Chanakya Arya, Chapter 4’

3.3 Project

Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos State, Nigeria

3.3.1 Project Particulars

Client: Quantum Luxury Properties LTD

Project cost: 100 billion

Consultant/ Structural Engineer: Ove Arup & Partners Nigeria LTD

Position held: Project Design Engineer

Period: 2 years

3.3.2 Project Description

The Metropolitan tower is a 29-storey building for residential purpose. The structure is 108.2m high. The basement level of the structure consists of carparks. The ground floor consists of gym, swimming pools (adult and kids), sit-out centres, cinema, driveway, multipurpose auditoriums as well as service rooms for generators and transformers. The suspended floors are post-tensioned flat slab systems supported by reinforced concrete columns, piers, and shear walls. The tower is composed of simplex floors covering (1st – 14th floor), lower and upper duplex floors covering (15th – 24th floors respectively), Pent-houses (25th – 27th floor), lower-level roof (28th floor) and upper roof level (29th floor).

3.3.3 Objective

To analyze, design and optimize the structural elements of the tower with a view to ensuring its stability, safety and durability during its service life.

3.3.4 Scope of the work

- i. Carry out preliminary/schematic and detailed structural engineering design for the building.
- ii. Preparation of specifications, structural detail drawings, and design calculations together with necessary guidance to assist in the construction phases.
- iii. Provide a formal letter of undertaking to the Planning Authority to confirm that the design was done by Arup Nigeria, and to see to the supervision of the structural works of the building construction from inception to completion.
- iv. Stamping and authenticating 5 sets of Structural Drawings with COREN stamp/seal. All drawings would bear Quantum Luxury Properties as well as Arup Nigeria's and other consultants' name to meet the planning regulation requirements.

Figure 9: Architecture 3D rendering of the Metropolitan Tower

Figure 10: Structural 3D model of the Metropolitan Tower

3.3.5 Applicable design standards and specifications

Category	Design codes	Descriptions
Loadings	BS 6399: Part 1 1996	Code of practice for dead and imposed loads
	BS 6399: Part 2 1997	Code of practice for wind loads
	BS 6399: Part 3 1988	Code of practice for imposed roof loads
Concrete	BS 8110: Part 1 1997	Code of practice for design & construction
	BS 8110: Part 3	Design charts for singly reinforced beams, doubly reinforced beams and rectangular column
	BS 8004:1986	Code of practice for foundations
Steel	BS 5950: Part 1 2000	Structural use of steel works in buildings
	BS 5950: Part 2 2000	Specification for materials, fabrication & erection
	BS 5950: Part 3 2000	Design in composite construction

3.3.6 Load Combinations

Combination		DL		LL		W	T	H
		Adverse	Beneficial	Advers	Beneficial			
1	DL+LL (+H)	1.4	1.0	1.6	-	-	-	1.2
2	DL+W (+H)	1.4	1.0	-	-	1.4	-	1.2
3	DL+LL+W (+H)	1.2	-	1.2	-	1.2	-	1.2
4	DL+LL+W+T (+H)	1.2	-	1.2	-	1.2	1.2	1.2

DL = dead load

LL = live load (imposed load) on floors W = wind load

T = temperature load

H = earth and water pressure

Figure 11: Typical structural slab of the Metropolitan Tower with loadings

Figure 12: 3D structural model of the Metropolitan Tower showing loadings

3.3.7 Applied Dead Loads

Allowances shall be made for anticipated floor finishes, ceiling and services (though not limited to these). The following assumptions have been made for this stage. The self-weight of the structural elements which by default will be generated by Tekla Structural Designer software.

Ceiling and Services	:	0.3KN/m ²
Screed and finishes	:	1.8 KN/ m ²
150/200 mm Sandcrete Block Wall	:	3.0 kN/m ² x floor height
Glazing / Curtain wall	:	1.5 KN/m (subject to manufacturer's specification)

3.3.8 Imposed Loads

The structure shall be designed for the imposed loads given in BS6399: Part 1. Accordingly, the following imposed loads have been used in the design:

Residency	:	1.5KN/m ²
Car Parking	:	2.5KN/m ²
Lobby	:	3.0KN/m ²
Services Plants	:	7.5KN/m ² (subject to manufacturers specification)
Entrance Lobby	:	4.0KN/m ²
Restaurants	:	3.0KN/m ²
Kitchen	:	3.0KN/m ²
Recreation Spaces	:	5.0KN/m ²
Gymnasium	:	5.0KN/m ²
Loading bay	:	5.0KN/m ²
Staircase	:	4.0KN/m ²
Ramps	:	5.0KN/m ²
Store	:	5.0KN/m ²
Terrace/Lobby	:	3.0KN/m ²
Swimming Pool	:	10.0KN/m ² x Height (subject to the Height of water)
Meeting Room	:	4.0 KN/m ²
Planters	:	15.0 KN/m ²

3.3.9 Wind Loading

Wind loading on the building shall be calculated using BS6399-2. Historically, wind speeds in Nigeria have been measured to three-second gusts. BS 6399-2 requires the adoption of hourly mean speeds in order to calculate the design pressures on the structure. In order to develop the design pressures on the structure, the 36m/s (3 secs gust wind speeds) need to be converted into hourly mean speeds, this can be conservatively done by dividing the metric three-second gust speed by 1.65.

The wind loadings have been derived in accordance with BS 6399 Part 2 in which the parameters include:

Basic wind speed for Lagos (V_s)	: 32 m/s (3 secs. gust wind speed)
Topographical factor (S_1)	: 1.0
Ground roughness (S_2)	: 0.90
Probability/Statistical factor (S_3)	: 1.0
Size effect factor (C_a)	: in accordance with BS 6399
External Pressure Co-efficient (C_{pe})	: in accordance with BS 6399
Internal Pressure Co-efficient (C_p)	: in accordance with BS 6399

3.3.10 Live Load Reduction

Floor live loads shall be reduced in accordance with BS6399-1. The following loads do not qualify for reduction. The reductions given in Table 4.1 below may be applied to the total imposed floor load in the design of columns, piers, walls and their supports and foundations, except for the cases stated above.

Number of floors with loads qualifying for reduction	% Reduction in total imposed loads
1	0
2	10
3	20
4	30
5 to 10	40
over 10	50

3.3.11 Notional Horizontal Forces

In addition to wind load, the structure will be designed to resist notional horizontal forces arising from construction in accordance with BS 8110 and BS 5950.

In summary these are:

- Concrete: 1.5% of unfactored dead loads (BS 8110 -1: 1997 3.1.4.2)
- Steel: 0.5% of factored dead and imposed loads on the referred level (BS5950 -2000 2.4.2.4)

3.3.12 Software package used

- Tekla Structural Designer
- Autodesk Revit Structure
- AutoCAD
- Tekla Tedds
- Reinforced Concrete Design Spread Sheets.

3.3.13 My involvement in the project

I worked as the project design engineer and carried out the following activities on the project:

- i. Prepared the General Arrangement (G.A) drawing for the project: schemed the positions of structural columns, beams, and load bearing walls in the structural layout.
- ii. Performed structural modeling, application of structural loads (dead: partitions, finishes, and services; imposed loads and wind loads), analysis, and design of the structure using Tekla Structural Designer software.
- iii. Designed the structural columns, staircases, beams, slabs, and pile-caps for the structure.
- iv. Generated design calculation reports for the project
- v. Generated reinforcement details for reinforced concrete elements.
- vi. Coordinated with the architect on the progressive design phases and agreement on sizes and positions of structural elements in the project.

3.3.14 Challenges encountered during the course of the project

- i. The team of architects (XBD Consultants) had several revisions/changes made on her architectural layout. This affected the structural modeling of the project both on Autodesk Revit and Tekla Structural Designer.
- ii. The basement and ground floor slab levels of the project had several structural slab levels (S.S.L).
- iii. Presence of planter arenas on the structural ground floor slab. This implied heavy loads and stresses on the slab.

3.3.15 Solutions proffered to the challenges encountered

- i. Effective coordination on Revit structure was implemented to keep track of revisions/changes made by the architects. Email trails were established to document updates alongside usage of revision clouds annotation on Revit Structure.
- ii. Reinforced concrete beams were introduced at the points of change in slab levels to allow for structural stability and support of the ground floor slab where these changes occur.
- iii. Extra structural piles were introduced at the specific locations where heavy planter fills were proposed by the architects. In addition, the structural slabs serving as pedestals for soil fills were adequately supported by stub columns to help control the deflection of the slab.

3.3.16 Experience gained

- i. Professional knowledge of structural column reinforcement and geometry telescoping with respect to axial load reduction from surfeit level to apex level of high-rise buildings.
- ii. Stability and robustness of high-rise building using shear walls and piers.
- iii. Improved knowledge on annotation of structural layouts using Autodesk Revit Structure. This involves marking up drawings for easy coordination and observation of revisions made by the architect.
- iv. Increased understanding of the analytical performance of structural elements under deformations and stresses. The graphical interaction of Tekla Structural Designer made it easy to see the analytical behavior of each structural elements via her animation capacity when viewing analytical results for members.

CHAPTER FOUR

4.0 CONCLUSION

This detailed report covers my professional engagements after I bagged a bachelor's degree in civil engineering with a first-class honours in the year 2019 from the Federal University of Technology, Akure (FUTA). I have been actively involved in projects that has required my inputs as a structural design engineer cutting across residential, commercial, religious and industrial structures. This continuous exposure to real time challenges has spurred my critical thinking skills to proffer sustainable solutions to various degrees of challenges in my area of professional expertise.

I certify that this report is written by me (Adeola Oluwaseyi ADELUWOYE) based on my professional experiences thus far from the projects I have worked on. I humbly request that my application for registration as a registered Engineer under the 'Council for the Regulation of Engineering in Nigeria – COREN) be favorably considered.

Name: Adeola Oluwaseyi ADELUWOYE

Signature

Date

APPENDICES

Appendix A - Design Calculations

Appendix B - Design Drawings

APPENDIX A - DESIGN CALCULATIONS

	Project MFM Campus Fellowship Building				Job Ref. Building	
	Structure Structural Beam				Sheet no. Page 1/4	
	Calc. by Adeola Adeluwoye	Date 23/07/2021	Chk'd by A.D.N	Date 30/11/2023	App'd by A.O.A	Date 30/11/2023

230 X 450 Beam

Static

230 X 450 Beam - 1 230x450 - Critical

Design summary bending top

Region	1	2	3
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	17.9 kNm	0.0 kNm	17.9 kNm
d	404.0 mm	404.0 mm	404.0 mm
d'	48.0 mm	48.0 mm	48.0 mm
K / K'	0.08	0.00	0.08
z	383.8 mm	0.0 mm	383.8 mm
A _{s,reqd}	107 mm ²	0 mm ²	107 mm ²
A _{slT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{s',reqd}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	107 mm ²	0 mm ²	107 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	135 mm ²	0 mm ²	135 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	402 mm ²	402 mm ²	402 mm ²
Top bars	2H16	2H16	2H16

Design summary bending bottom

Region	1	2	3
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	36.5 kNm	71.5 kNm	36.5 kNm
d	402.0 mm	402.0 mm	402.0 mm
d'	46.0 mm	46.0 mm	46.0 mm
K / K'	0.16	0.31	0.16
z	381.9 mm	379.2 mm	381.9 mm
A _{s,reqd}	219 mm ²	433 mm ²	219 mm ²
A _{slT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{s',reqd}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	219 mm ²	433 mm ²	219 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	144 mm ²	135 mm ²	144 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	628 mm ²	628 mm ²	628 mm ²
Bottom bars	2H20	2H20	2H20
Deflection check	-	(L / d) _{actual} = 11.940 < 29.788	-

Design summary shear and torsion

Region	Centre
Length	5.030 m
Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
V	47.8 kN
V _{max}	462.3 kN
V _c	60.0 kN
(A _{svs} / S _{vs}) _{reqd}	0 mm ² /m
(A _{sv} / S _v) _{prov}	335 mm ² /m
T	0.00 kNm
T _{F,max}	462.3 kN
T _F	0.0 kN

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural Beam			Page 2/4			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Region	Centre
$(A_{svt} / S_{vt})_{reqd}$	0 mm ² /m
Links	2H8-300

Loading

Loadcase	Source	Direction	In Proj.	Span/Stack	Type	Q _i [kN/m]	Pos [m]	Length [m]
1 Self weight - excluding slabs	User	Global Z		1	UDL	2.4	0.000	5.030
3 Dead	User	Global Z		1	Full UDL	9.1		5.030
4 Imposed	User	Global Z		1	Full UDL	4.2		5.030

Head code: United Kingdom (BS), design code: BS 8110-1 (1997)

Static

230 X 450 Beam - 1 230x450 - Critical

Longitudinal Bars - Critical

Top: 0.000 - 1.258 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.266$

Provided tension bars: 2H16

Pass

Compression steel utilization ratio $A_{s' reqd} / A_{s' prov} = 0.000$

Provided compression bars: 2H20

Pass

Bottom: 0.755 - 4.276 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.690$

Provided tension bars: 2H20

Pass

Compression steel utilization ratio $A_{s' reqd} / A_{s' prov} = 0.000$

Provided compression bars: 2H16

Pass

	Project				Job Ref.	
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building				Building	
	Structure				Sheet no.	
Structural Beam				Page 3/4		
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Deflection Check - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Beam width $b_w = 230.0$ mm

Effective depth in region $d = 402.0$ mm

Clear span length $L = 4.800$ m

Span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{basic} = 20.000$

Modification factor (Tension) $MF_t = \text{MIN}[0.55 + ((477 - f_c) / (120 \times (0.9 + (M / (b_w \times d^2))))), 2.0] = 1.322$

Modification factor (Compression) $MF_c = \text{MIN}[(1 + ((100 \times A_s'_{prov}) / (b_w \times d))) / (3 + (100 \times A_s'_{prov}) / (b_w \times d)), 1.5] = 1.127$

Maximum allowable span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{max} = (L / d)_{basic} \times MF_t \times MF_c = 29.788$

Actual span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{actual} = 11.940$

Deflection check: $(L / d)_{actual} \leq (L / d)_{max}$

Pass

Increase reinforcement if deflection fails : Not required

BS 8110-1:1997 Section 3.4.6.3
Table 3.9

BS 8110-1:1997 Section 3.4.6.5
Table 3.10 equation 7

BS 8110-1:1997 Section 3.4.6.6
Table 3.11 equation 9

BS 8110-1:1997 Section 3.4.6.6

BS 8110-1:1997 Section
3.4.6.5

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural Beam			Page 4/4			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Shear Links - Critical

0.000 - 5.030 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Link Checks - Critical

Link utilization ratio $(A_{sv} / S_v)_{reqd} / (A_{sv} / S_v)_{prov} =$
0.000

Pass

$(A_{sv} / S_v)_{prov} \geq (A_{svs} / S_{vs})_{min}$

Pass

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural Column			Page 1/6			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

230 x 230 Column

Head code: United Kingdom (BS), design code: BS 8110-1 (1997)

Static

Stack 2 230x230 - Critical

Longitudinal Bars - Critical

FE Chase Down - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Bottom - Critical

Axial force $N = 140.0 \text{ kN}$
 Moment about major axis $M_{\text{major}} = 11.6 \text{ kNm}$
 Moment about minor axis $M_{\text{minor}} = 9.2 \text{ kNm}$
 Major moment resistance $M_{\text{major,res}} = M_{\text{major,res,conc}} + M_{\text{major,res,steel}} = 26.0 \text{ kNm}$
 Minor moment resistance $M_{\text{minor,res}} = M_{\text{minor,res,conc}} + M_{\text{minor,res,steel}} = 20.8 \text{ kNm}$
 Moment resistance ratio $\frac{M_{\text{major}}^2 + M_{\text{minor}}^2}{M_{\text{major,res}}^2 + M_{\text{minor,res}}^2} = 0.444$

Pass

Shear Links - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Minor Load Direction - Critical

No Shear Reinforcement required

Pass

Stack 1 230x230 - Critical

Longitudinal Bars - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Mid-fifth - Critical

Axial force $N = 390.6 \text{ kN}$
 Moment about major axis $M_{\text{major}} = -31.9 \text{ kNm}$
 Moment about minor axis $M_{\text{minor}} = -29.6 \text{ kNm}$
 Major moment resistance $M_{\text{major,res}} = M_{\text{major,res,conc}} + M_{\text{major,res,steel}} = -38.2 \text{ kNm}$
 Minor moment resistance $M_{\text{minor,res}} = M_{\text{minor,res,conc}} + M_{\text{minor,res,steel}} = -35.3 \text{ kNm}$
 Moment resistance ratio $\frac{M_{\text{major}}^2 + M_{\text{minor}}^2}{M_{\text{major,res}}^2 + M_{\text{minor,res}}^2} = 0.836$

Pass

Shear Links - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Major Load Direction - Critical

No Shear Reinforcement required

Pass

Axial Force Diagram, First-order linear

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural Column			Page 2/6			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Loadcase: 1 Self weight - excluding slabs, Axial Force for 230 x 230 Column

Loadcase: 2 Slab self weight, Axial Force for 230 x 230 Column

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural Column			Page 3/6			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Loadcase: 3 Dead, Axial Force for 230 x 230 Column

Loadcase: 4 Imposed, Axial Force for 230 x 230 Column

Interaction Diagrams

Static

Project			MFM Campus Fellowship Building		Job Ref.		Building			
Structure			Structural Column			Sheet no.			Page 4/6	
Calc. by		Date	Chk'd by		Date	App'd by		Date		
Adeola Adeluwoye		23/07/2021	A.D.N		30/11/2023	A.O.A		30/11/2023		

N-M Interaction Diagram

*M-M Interaction Diagram at $N = 140.0$ kN
6 (Final) $Cb_1-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI$, FE Chase Down*

Project MFM Campus Fellowship Building				Job Ref. Building	
Structure Structural Column				Sheet no. Page 5/6	
Calc. by Adeola Adeluwoye	Date 23/07/2021	Chk'd by A.D.N	Date 30/11/2023	App'd by A.O.A	Date 30/11/2023

N-M Interaction Diagram

M-M Interaction Diagram at N = 390.6 kN

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI, 3D Building Analysis

Static

Longitudinal Bars Summary

Stack	Section	Longitudinal Bars	Analysis	Combination	Critical position	Ratio	Status
2	230x230	4H16	FE Chase Down	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	Bottom	0.444	Pass
1	230x230	4H25	3D Building Analysis	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	Mid-fifth	0.836	Pass

Links Summary

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural Column			Page 6/6			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Stack	Section	Span links	Analysis	Combination	Ratio	Status
2	230x230	1H10-175	3D Building Analysis	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	0.000	Pass
1	230x230	1H10-300	3D Building Analysis	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	0.000	Pass

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Pad footing			Page 1/2			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Pad footing

Static & RSA

Applied Loads Summary

	Strength	Service
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
P	953.3 kN	661.7 kN
F _{x,sup}	2.9 kN	2.1 kN
F _{y,sup}	1.5 kN	1.1 kN
M _{x,sup}	0.0 kNm	0.0 kNm
M _{y,sup}	0.0 kNm	0.0 kNm
Added Loads		
F _{swt}	39.0 kN	
F _{soil}	0.0 kN	
F _{Gsur}	0.0 kN	
F _{Qsur}	0.0 kN	

Foundation Details

Foundation Type	Pad Base
Concrete Class	C30
Size	2200mm × 2200mm
Overall Depth	350.0 mm
Top Cover	40.0 mm
Bottom Cover	40.0 mm
Side Cover	40.0 mm
Depth From Surface	0.0 mm

Bearing Capacity - Critical

Summary

Size	2200.0 × 2200.0
Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
q _{max}	145.4 kN/m ²
q _a	150.0 kN/m ²
Ratio	0.969

Bending Capacity

Summary

Direction	X-Bot	Y-Bot
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
m _u	95.647 kNm/m	71.303 kNm/m
d	286.0 mm	302.0 mm
K / K'	0.250	0.167
z	271.7 mm	286.9 mm
A _{s,reqd}	809 mm ² /m	571 mm ² /m
A _{s,prov}	1005 mm ² /m	894 mm ² /m
A _{s,min}	455 mm ² /m	455 mm ² /m
Ratio	0.805	0.639

Shear Capacity

Summary

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Pad footing			Page 2/2			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Direction	X	Y
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
V _{su}	0.358 N/mm ²	0.482 N/mm ²
V _{max}	4.382 N/mm ²	4.382 N/mm ²
V _{res}	0.480 N/mm ²	0.515 N/mm ²
Ratio	0.746	0.935

Punching Shear

Summary

Analysis	Combination	Perimeter	u ₀ / u _n [mm]	v _{eff} [N/mm ²]	v _{max} / v _{res} [N/mm ²]	Ratio	Status
3D Building Analysis	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	Loaded	1460.0	2.168	4.382	0.495	Pass
3D Building Analysis	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	At 1.5d	3447.0	0.455	0.498	0.914	Pass

Uplift

Summary

Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	6 (Final) Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
P	0.0 kN
F _{G,stab}	0.0 kN
Ratio	0.000

Static & RSA

Bearing Capacity - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Vertical force from analysis

$$P = -661.7 \text{ kN}$$

Additional foundation load

$$F = \gamma_{FG,0} \times F_{swt} + \gamma_{FG,soil} \times F_{soil} + \gamma_{FG,sur} \times F_{Gsur} + \gamma_{FQ,sur} \times F_{Qsur} = 39.0 \text{ kN}$$

Base reaction

$$T = F - P = 700.8 \text{ kN}$$

Moment about X axis

$$M_{x,c} = M_{x,sup} - (P \times e_{py}) - (h \times F_{y,sup}) = -0.4 \text{ kNm}$$

Moment about Y axis

$$M_{y,c} = M_{y,sup} + (P \times e_{px}) + (h \times F_{x,sup}) = 0.7 \text{ kNm}$$

Eccentricity in X direction

$$e_{Tx} = M_{y,c} / T = 1.1 \text{ mm}$$

Eccentricity in Y direction

$$e_{Ty} = -M_{x,c} / T = 0.5 \text{ mm}$$

Length in X direction

$$L_x = 2.200 \text{ m}$$

Length in Y direction

$$L_y = 2.200 \text{ m}$$

$$(|e_{Tx}| / L_x) + (|e_{Ty}| / L_y) \leq 1 / 6$$

Base reaction acts within middle third of

base - no loss of contact

Base area

$$A = L_x \times L_y = 4.84E+06 \text{ mm}^2$$

Pad base pressure q₁

$$q_1 = (T / A) - (6 \times M_{y,c} / (L_x \times A)) + (6 \times M_{x,c} / (L_y \times A)) = 144.2 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Pad base pressure q₂

$$q_2 = (T / A) - (6 \times M_{y,c} / (L_x \times A)) - (6 \times M_{x,c} / (L_y \times A)) = 144.6 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Pad base pressure q₃

$$q_3 = (T / A) + (6 \times M_{y,c} / (L_x \times A)) + (6 \times M_{x,c} / (L_y \times A)) = 145.0 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Pad base pressure q₄

$$q_4 = (T / A) + (6 \times M_{y,c} / (L_x \times A)) - (6 \times M_{x,c} / (L_y \times A)) = 145.4 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Maximum pad base pressure

$$q_{max} = \text{MAX}[q_1, q_2, q_3, q_4] = 145.4 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Maximum allowable bearing pressure

$$q_a = 150.0 \text{ kN/m}^2$$

Bearing capacity utilization ratio

$$q_{max} / q_a = \mathbf{0.969}$$

Pass

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural slab			Page 1/3			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Slab: S 9, Panel: Slab

Static & RSA

Reinforcement Design Summary

Reinforcement Layer	Reinforcement Provided	Area Provided [mm ² /m]	Area Required [mm ² /m]	Utilization
Bottom-X	H12-150.0-B1	754	254	0.336
Bottom-Y	H12-150.0-B2	754	258	0.343
Top-X	H12-150.0-T1	754	553	0.733
Top-Y	H12-150.0-T2	754	564	0.748

Static & RSA

Reinforcement Design Details

Bottom-X

Summary

Utilization ratio $A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.336$

Analysis method First-order linear

Critical combination 6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI

Pass

Moment Capacity Check

$A_{s,prov}$ X Bottom 754 mm²/m

M_{dx} Bottom -14.567 kNm/m

$A_{s,req}$ X Bottom 254 mm²/m

Utilization ratio $A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.336$

Pass

Limiting Reinforcement Parameters Checks

Check Minimum Diameter Pass

Check Maximum Diameter Pass

Check Minimum Bar Distance Pass

Check Maximum Spacing Tension Bars Pass

Check Minimum Area of Reinforcement Pass

Check Maximum Area of Reinforcement Pass

Bottom-Y

Summary

Utilization ratio $A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.343$

Analysis method First-order linear

Critical combination 6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI

Pass

Moment Capacity Check

$A_{s,prov}$ Y Bottom 754 mm²/m

M_{dy} Bottom -13.561 kNm/m

$A_{s,req}$ Y Bottom 258 mm²/m

Utilization ratio $A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.343$

Pass

Limiting Reinforcement Parameters Checks

Check Minimum Diameter Pass

Check Maximum Diameter Pass

Check Minimum Bar Distance Pass

Check Maximum Spacing Tension Bars Pass

Check Minimum Area of Reinforcement Pass

Check Maximum Area of Reinforcement Pass

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural slab			Page 2/3			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

Top-X

Summary

Utilization ratio **$A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.733$**
 Analysis method Grillage chase-down
 Critical combination 6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI

Pass

Moment Capacity Check

$A_{s,prov}$ X Top 754 mm²/m
 M_{dX} Top 31.752 kNm/m
 $A_{s,req}$ X Top 553 mm²/m
 Utilization ratio **$A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.733$**

Pass

Limiting Reinforcement Parameters Checks

Check Minimum Diameter Pass
 Check Maximum Diameter Pass
 Check Minimum Bar Distance Pass
 Check Maximum Spacing Tension Bars Pass
 Check Minimum Area of Reinforcement Pass
 Check Maximum Area of Reinforcement Pass

Top-Y

Summary

Utilization ratio **$A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.748$**
 Analysis method FE chase-down
 Critical combination 6 (Final) Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI

Pass

Moment Capacity Check

$A_{s,prov}$ Y Top 754 mm²/m
 M_{dY} Top 29.467 kNm/m
 $A_{s,req}$ Y Top 564 mm²/m
 Utilization ratio **$A_{s,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.748$**

Pass

Limiting Reinforcement Parameters Checks

Check Minimum Diameter Pass
 Check Maximum Diameter Pass
 Check Minimum Bar Distance Pass
 Check Maximum Spacing Tension Bars Pass
 Check Minimum Area of Reinforcement Pass
 Check Maximum Area of Reinforcement Pass

Span - Effective Depth Check

Pass

Span Characteristic X Valid
 Span Characteristic Y Valid
 Span Direction Y
 Span Characteristic Valid
 Edge Category Start Dis-continuous support
 Edge Category End Dis-continuous support
 $A_{st,reqd}$ 258 mm²/m
 $A_{s2,reqd}$ 564 mm²/m
 $A_{st,prov}$ 754 mm²/m
 L/d 39.606

	Project			Job Ref.		
	MFM Campus Fellowship Building			Building		
	Structure			Sheet no.		
Structural slab			Page 3/3			
Calc. by	Date	Chk'd by	Date	App'd by	Date	
Adeola Adeluwoye	23/07/2021	A.D.N	30/11/2023	A.O.A	30/11/2023	

$(L/d)_{max} * MF_t$ 40.000

STEEL DESIGN

CODE: *British Standard BS 5950:2000*

ANALYSIS TYPE: *Code Group Verification*

CODE GROUP: *3 Front cantilever UB*

MEMBER: *15 Beam_15*

POINT: *2*

COORDINATE: *x = 0.50 L = 0.80 m*

LOADS:

*Governing Load Case: 4 ULS /1/ 1*1.40 + 2*1.40 + 3*1.60*

MATERIAL

S275

$p_y = 275.00 \text{ MPa}$

$E = 205000.00 \text{ MPa}$

SECTION PARAMETERS: UB 254x146x31

$D = 251 \text{ mm}$

$B = 146 \text{ mm}$

$t = 6 \text{ mm}$

$T = 9 \text{ mm}$

$A_y = 2513 \text{ mm}^2$

$I_y = 44130000 \text{ mm}^4$

$W_{ely} = 351074 \text{ mm}^3$

$A_z = 1508 \text{ mm}^2$

$I_z = 4480000 \text{ mm}^4$

$W_{elz} = 61328 \text{ mm}^3$

$A = 3970 \text{ mm}^2$

$I_x = 85500 \text{ mm}^4$

INTERNAL FORCES

$M_{lt} = -11.57 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$mlt = 1.00$

$M_y = -2.89 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$M_{y\max} = -11.57 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$F_{vz} = -7.23 \text{ kN}$

CAPACITIES

Section class = 1

$M_{cy} = 108.63 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$M_{ey} = 96.55 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$P_{vz} = 248.89 \text{ kN}$

LATERAL BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

$Le = 1.28 \text{ m}$

$x = 29.61$

$u = 0.88$

$v = 0.98$

$\Lambda_{mLT} = 32.92$

$M_b = 108.63 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

About Y axis:

About Z axis:

VERIFICATION FORMULAS:

Section check

$M_y/M_{cy} = 0.03 < 1.00 \quad (4.8.3.2)$

$F_{vz}/P_{vz} = 0.03 < 1.00 \quad (4.2.3)$

Member stability check

$mlt \cdot M_{lt}/M_b = 0.11 < 1.00 \quad (4.3.6.2)$

Section OK !!!

STEEL DESIGN

CODE: *British Standard BS 5950:2000*

ANALYSIS TYPE: *Code Group Verification*

CODE GROUP: *5 Main bottom CHS*

MEMBER: *20 Column_20* **POINT:** *3*

COORDINATE: *x = 1.00 L = 2.90 m*

LOADS:

*Governing Load Case: 4 ULS /1/ 1*1.40 + 2*1.40 + 3*1.60*

MATERIAL

S275

$p_y = 275.00 \text{ MPa}$

$E = 205000.00 \text{ MPa}$

SECTION PARAMETERS: CHS 244.5x6.3

$D = 245 \text{ mm}$

$t = 6 \text{ mm}$

$A_y = 2826 \text{ mm}^2$

$I_y = 33460000 \text{ mm}^4$

$W_{ely} = 273701 \text{ mm}^3$

$A_z = 2826 \text{ mm}^2$

$I_z = 33460000 \text{ mm}^4$

$W_{elz} = 273701 \text{ mm}^3$

$A = 4710 \text{ mm}^2$

$I_x = 66920000 \text{ mm}^4$

INTERNAL FORCES

$F_c = 396.64 \text{ kN}$

$M_{lt} = 33.35 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$m_{lt} = 1.00$

$M_y = 33.35 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$M_{y\max} = 33.35 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$m_y = 0.62$

$M_z = -13.85 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$M_{z\max} = 17.70 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$m_z = 0.44$

$F_{vy} = 10.88 \text{ kN}$

$F_{vz} = 10.94 \text{ kN}$

$m_{yz} = 0.44$

CAPACITIES

$P_c = 1295.25 \text{ kN}$

Section class = 1

$M_{cy} = 98.32 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$M_{ey} = 75.27 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$M_{cz} = 98.32 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$M_{ez} = 75.27 \text{ kN}\cdot\text{m}$

$P_{vy} = 466.29 \text{ kN}$

$P_{vz} = 466.29 \text{ kN}$

LATERAL BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

About Y axis:

$L_y = 2.90 \text{ m}$

$L_{ey} = 2.90 \text{ m}$

$L_{amy} = 34.41$

$n_y = 0.03$

$p_{ey} = 1709.08 \text{ MPa}$

$F_{iy} = 1021.53 \text{ MPa}$

$p_y = 264.22 \text{ MPa}$

$P_{cy} = 1244.46 \text{ kN}$

About Z axis:

$L_z = 2.90 \text{ m}$

$L_{ez} = 2.90 \text{ m}$

$L_{amz} = 34.41$

$n_z = 0.03$

$p_{ez} = 1709.08 \text{ MPa}$

$F_{iz} = 1021.53 \text{ MPa}$

$p_z = 264.22 \text{ MPa}$

$P_{cz} = 1244.46 \text{ kN}$

VERIFICATION FORMULAS:

Section check

$F_c/P_c + M_y/M_{cy} + M_z/M_{cz} = 0.79 < 1.00 \quad (4.8.3.2)$

$F_{vy}/P_{vy} = 0.02 < 1.00 \quad (4.2.3) \quad F_{vz}/P_{vz} = 0.02 < 1.00 \quad (4.2.3)$

Member stability check

$F_c/P_{cy} + (1 + 0.5 \cdot F_c/P_{cy}) \cdot m_y \cdot M_{y\max}/M_{cy} + 0.5 \cdot m_{yz} \cdot M_{z\max}/M_{cz} = 0.60 < 1.00 \quad (4.8.3.3.c)$

Section OK !!!

STEEL DESIGN

CODE: *British Standard BS 5950:2000*

ANALYSIS TYPE: *Code Group Verification*

CODE GROUP: *1 Distribution SHS*

MEMBER: *8 Beam_8*

POINT: *2*

COORDINATE: *x = 0.50 L = 4.75 m*

LOADS:

*Governing Load Case: 4 ULS /1/ 1*1.40 + 2*1.40 + 3*1.60*

MATERIAL

S275

$f_y = 275.00$ MPa

$E = 205000.00$ MPa

SECTION PARAMETERS: SHS 250x250x8

D=250 mm

B=250 mm

t=8 mm

T=8 mm

$A_y = 3760$ mm²

$I_y = 72290000$ mm⁴

$W_{ely} = 578320$ mm³

$A_z = 3760$ mm²

$I_z = 72290000$ mm⁴

$W_{elz} = 578320$ mm³

$A = 7520$ mm²

$I_x = 115980000$ mm⁴

INTERNAL FORCES

$F_t = -1.89$ kN

$M_{lt} = 101.71$ kN*m

$mlt = 1.00$

$M_y = 101.71$ kN*m

$M_{ymax} = 101.71$ kN*m

$M_z = 8.00$ kN*m

$M_{zmax} = 15.99$ kN*m

$F_{vy} = 1.68$ kN

$F_{vz} = 0.96$ kN

CAPACITIES

$P_t = 2068.00$ kN

Section class = 2

$M_{cy} = 185.90$ kN*m

$M_{ey} = 159.04$ kN*m

$M_{cz} = 185.90$ kN*m

$M_{ez} = 159.04$ kN*m

$P_{vy} = 620.40$ kN

$P_{vz} = 620.40$ kN

LATERAL BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

About Y axis:

About Z axis:

VERIFICATION FORMULAS:

Section check

$F_t/P_t + M_y/M_{cy} + M_z/M_{cz} = 0.59 < 1.00$ (4.8.2.2)

$F_{vy}/P_{vy} = 0.00 < 1.00$ (4.2.3) $F_{vz}/P_{vz} = 0.00 < 1.00$ (4.2.3)

Member stability check

Not analyzed

Section OK !!!

STEEL DESIGN

CODE: *British Standard BS 5950:2000*

ANALYSIS TYPE: *Code Group Verification*

CODE GROUP: *2 Main SHS*

MEMBER: *24 Beam_24*

POINT: *1*

COORDINATE: *x = 0.19 L = 2.50 m*

LOADS:

*Governing Load Case: 4 ULS /1/ 1*1.40 + 2*1.40 + 3*1.60*

MATERIAL

S275

$f_y = 275.00$ MPa

$E = 205000.00$ MPa

SECTION PARAMETERS: SHSC 250x250x8

D=250 mm

B=250 mm

t=8 mm

T=8 mm

$A_y = 3760$ mm²

$I_y = 72290000$ mm⁴

$W_{ely} = 578320$ mm³

$A_z = 3760$ mm²

$I_z = 72290000$ mm⁴

$W_{elz} = 578320$ mm³

$A = 7520$ mm²

$I_x = 115980000$ mm⁴

INTERNAL FORCES

$F_t = -341.59$ kN

$M_{lt} = -141.37$ kN*m

$mlt = 1.00$

$M_y = -141.37$ kN*m

$M_{ymax} = -141.37$ kN*m

$M_z = -5.78$ kN*m

$M_{zmax} = 18.00$ kN*m

$F_{vy} = -6.39$ kN

$F_{vz} = 97.87$ kN

CAPACITIES

$P_t = 2068.00$ kN

Section class = 2

$M_{cy} = 185.90$ kN*m

$M_{ey} = 159.04$ kN*m

$M_{cz} = 185.90$ kN*m

$M_{ez} = 159.04$ kN*m

$P_{vy} = 620.40$ kN

$P_{vz} = 620.40$ kN

LATERAL BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

BUCKLING PARAMETERS:

About Y axis:

About Z axis:

VERIFICATION FORMULAS:

Section check

$F_t/P_t + M_y/M_{cy} + M_z/M_{cz} = 0.96 < 1.00$ (4.8.2.2)

$F_{vy}/P_{vy} = 0.01 < 1.00$ (4.2.3) $F_{vz}/P_{vz} = 0.16 < 1.00$ (4.2.3)

Member stability check

Not analyzed

Section OK !!!

Project				Job no.	
METROPOLITAN TOWER				N5205	
Calcs for				Start page no./Revision	
FRONT SIDE CANOPY				1	
Calcs by	Calcs date	Checked by	Checked date	Approved by	Approved date
AOA	03/04/2023	ADN/ ATF	03/04/2023	NCO	03/04/2023

STEEL BEAM ANALYSIS & DESIGN (BS5950)

In accordance with BS5950-1:2000 incorporating Corrigendum No.1

TEDDS calculation version 3.0.07

Support conditions

Support A	Vertically restrained
	Rotationally free
Support B	Vertically restrained
	Rotationally free
Support C	Vertically free
	Rotationally free

Applied loading

Beam loads	Dead self weight of beam × 1
Span 1 loads	Dead UDL 9.96 kN/m from 0 mm to 9420 mm

Project				Job no.	
METROPOLITAN TOWER				N5205	
Calcs for				Start page no./Revision	
FRONT SIDE CANOPY				2	
Calcs by	Calcs date	Checked by	Checked date	Approved by	Approved date
AOA	03/04/2023	ADN/ ATF	03/04/2023	NCO	03/04/2023

Span 2 loads

Imposed UDL 1.5 kN/m from 0 mm to 9420 mm
 Dead UDL 9.96 kN/m from 0 mm to 1705 mm
 Imposed UDL 1.5 kN/m from 0 mm to 1705 mm

Load combinations

Load combination 1 - ULS

Support A
 Dead × 1.40
 Imposed × 1.60
 Dead × 1.40
 Imposed × 1.60

Support B
 Dead × 1.40
 Imposed × 1.60
 Dead × 1.40
 Imposed × 1.60

Load combination 2 - SLS

Support C
 Dead × 1.40
 Imposed × 1.60

Support A
 Dead × 1.00
 Imposed × 1.00
 Dead × 1.00
 Imposed × 1.00

Support B
 Dead × 1.00
 Imposed × 1.00
 Dead × 1.00
 Imposed × 1.00

Support C
 Dead × 1.00
 Imposed × 1.00

Analysis results

Maximum moment	$M_{max} = 182.5$ kNm	$M_{min} = -25.6$ kNm
Maximum moment span 1	$M_{s1_max} = 182.5$ kNm	$M_{s1_min} = -25.6$ kNm
Maximum moment span 2	$M_{s2_max} = 0$ kNm	$M_{s2_min} = -25.6$ kNm
Maximum shear	$V_{max} = 80.1$ kN	$V_{min} = -85.5$ kN
Maximum shear span 1	$V_{s1_max} = 80.1$ kN	$V_{s1_min} = -85.5$ kN
Maximum shear span 2	$V_{s2_max} = 30$ kN	$V_{s2_min} = 0$ kN
Deflection	$\delta_{max} = 7.8$ mm	$\delta_{min} = 4.2$ mm
Deflection span 1	$\delta_{s1_max} = 7.8$ mm	$\delta_{s1_min} = 0$ mm
Deflection span 2	$\delta_{s2_max} = 0$ mm	$\delta_{s2_min} = 4.2$ mm
Maximum reaction at support A	$R_{A_max} = 80.1$ kN	$R_{A_min} = 56.2$ kN
Unfactored dead load reaction at support A	$R_{A_Dead} = 49.4$ kN	
Unfactored imposed load reaction at support A	$R_{A_Imposed} = 6.8$ kN	
Maximum reaction at support B	$R_{B_max} = 115.5$ kN	$R_{B_min} = 81.1$ kN
Unfactored dead load reaction at support B	$R_{B_Dead} = 71.2$ kN	
Unfactored imposed load reaction at support B	$R_{B_Imposed} = 9.9$ kN	
Maximum reaction at support C	$R_{C_max} = 0$ kN	$R_{C_min} = 0$ kN

Section details

Section type **RHS 250x150x16.0 (Tata Steel Celsius (Gr355 Gr420 Gr460))**
 Steel grade **S275**
From table 9: Design strength p_y

Project METROPOLITAN TOWER				Job no. N5205	
Calcs for FRONT SIDE CANOPY				Start page no./Revision 3	
Calcs by AOA	Calcs date 03/04/2023	Checked by ADN/ ATF	Checked date 03/04/2023	Approved by NCO	Approved date 03/04/2023

Thickness of element
Design strength
Modulus of elasticity

$t = 16.0$ mm
 $p_y = 275$ N/mm²
 $E = 205000$ N/mm²

Lateral restraint

Span 1 has full lateral restraint
Span 2 has full lateral restraint
Cantilever tip is free
Cantilever support is continuous with lateral and torsional restraint

Effective length factors

Effective length factor in major axis $K_x = 1.00$
Effective length factor in minor axis $K_y = 1.00$
Effective length factor for lateral-torsional buckling $K_{LT,A} = 1.00$
 $K_{LT,B} = 1.00$
 $K_{LT,C} = 1.00$

Classification of cross sections - Section 3.5

$$\varepsilon = \sqrt{[275 \text{ N/mm}^2 / p_y]} = 1.00$$

Web - major axis - Table 12

Depth of section $d = D - 3 \times t = 202$ mm
 $d / t = 12.6 \times \varepsilon \leq 64 \times \varepsilon$ Class 1 plastic

Flange - major axis - Table 12

Width of section $b = B - 3 \times t = 102$ mm
 $b / t = 6.4 \times \varepsilon \leq \min(28 \times \varepsilon, 80 \times \varepsilon - d / t)$ Class 1 plastic
Section is class 1 plastic

Shear capacity - Section 4.2.3

Design shear force $F_v = \max(\text{abs}(V_{\max}), \text{abs}(V_{\min})) = 85.5$ kN
 $(D - 3 \times t) / t < 70 \times \varepsilon$

Web does not need to be checked for shear buckling

Shear area $A_v = A \times D / (D + B) = 7188$ mm²

Design shear resistance $P_v = 0.6 \times p_y \times A_v = 1186.1$ kN

PASS - Design shear resistance exceeds design shear force

Project				Job no.	
METROPOLITAN TOWER				N5205	
Calcs for				Start page no./Revision	
FRONT SIDE CANOPY				4	
Calcs by	Calcs date	Checked by	Checked date	Approved by	Approved date
AOA	03/04/2023	ADN/ ATF	03/04/2023	NCO	03/04/2023

Moment capacity at span 1 - Section 4.2.5

Design bending moment

$$M = \max(\text{abs}(M_{s1_max}), \text{abs}(M_{s1_min})) = \mathbf{182.5 \text{ kNm}}$$

Moment capacity low shear - cl.4.2.5.2

$$M_c = \min(p_y \times S_{xx}, 1.5 \times p_y \times Z_{xx}) = \mathbf{249.1 \text{ kNm}}$$

PASS - Moment capacity exceeds design bending moment

Check vertical deflection - Section 2.5.2

Consider deflection due to imposed loads

Limiting deflection

$$\delta_{lim} = L_{s1} / 250 = \mathbf{37.68 \text{ mm}}$$

Maximum deflection span 1

$$\delta = \max(\text{abs}(\delta_{max}), \text{abs}(\delta_{min})) = \mathbf{7.786 \text{ mm}}$$

PASS - Maximum deflection does not exceed deflection limit

	Project Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos			Job Ref. N5205	
	Structure Rc Beam for Canopy Steel Structure			Sheet no. Page 1/9	
	Calc. by Adeola.Adeluwoye	Date 10/07/2024	Chk'd by A.D.N	Date 18/04/2024	App'd by N.C.O

Canopy Beam

Regional code: United Kingdom (BS), design code: BS 8110-1 (1997)

Static Design Calculations

Canopy Beam - 1 230x900 - Critical

Longitudinal Bars - Critical

Top: 1.187 - 2.373 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.212$

Provided tension bars: 2H20

Pass

Compression steel utilization ratio $A_{s',reqd} / A_{s',prov} = 0.000$

Provided compression bars: 2H16

Pass

Bottom: 0.000 - 2.373 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.036$

Provided tension bars: 2H16

Pass

Compression steel utilization ratio $A_{s',reqd} / A_{s',prov} = 0.000$

Provided compression bars: 2H16

Pass

Deflection Check - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Beam width $b_w = 230.0$ mm

Effective depth in $d = 850.0$ mm

region

Clear span length $L = 2.258$ m

Span/effective depth $(L/d)_{basic} = 7.000$

ratio

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.3
Table 3.9

	Project Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos				Job Ref. N5205	
	Structure Rc Beam for Canopy Steel Structure				Sheet no. Page 2/9	
	Calc. by Adeola.Adeluwoye	Date 10/07/2024	Chk'd by A.D.N	Date 18/04/2024	App'd by N.C.O	Date 18/04/2024

Modification factor (Tension) $MF_t = \text{MIN}[0.55 + ((477 - f_c) / (120 \times (0.9 + (M / (b_w \times d^2))))), 2.0] = 2.000$

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.5
Table 3.10 equation
7

Modification factor (Compression) $MF_c = \text{MIN}[(1 + ((100 \times A_s'_{prov}) / (b_w \times d))) / (3 + (100 \times A_s'_{prov}) / (b_w \times d)), 1.5] = 1.064$

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.6
Table 3.11 equation
9

Maximum allowable span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{max} = (L / d)_{basic} \times MF_t \times MF_c = 14.898$

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.6
BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.5

Actual span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{actual} = 2.657$

Deflection check: $(L / d)_{actual} \leq (L / d)_{max}$

✓ Pass
Increase reinforcement if deflection fails : Not required

Shear Links - Critical

0.000 - 1.780 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Link Checks - Critical

Link utilization ratio $(A_{sv} / S_v)_{reqd} / (A_{sv} / S_v)_{prov} = 0.000$

✓ Pass
 $(A_{sv} / S_v)_{prov} \geq (A_{sv} / S_v)_{nom}$

✓ Pass

Canopy Beam - 2 230x900 - Critical

Longitudinal Bars - Critical

Top: 6.202 - 8.269 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.302$

Provided tension bars: 2H20

✓ Pass
Compression steel utilization ratio $A_s'_{reqd} / A_s'_{prov} = 0.000$

Provided compression bars: 4H25

✓ Pass

Bottom: 1.240 - 7.029 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.298$

Provided tension bars: 4H25

✓ Pass
Compression steel utilization ratio $A_s'_{reqd} / A_s'_{prov} = 0.000$

Provided compression bars: 2H20

✓ Pass

Deflection Check - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

	Project Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos				Job Ref. N5205	
	Structure Rc Beam for Canopy Steel Structure				Sheet no. Page 3/9	
	Calc. by Adeola.Adeluwoye	Date 10/07/2024	Chk'd by A.D.N	Date 18/04/2024	App'd by N.C.O	Date 18/04/2024

Beam width $b_w = 230.0$ mm
Effective depth in region $d = 822.5$ mm
Clear span length $L = 8.039$ m
Span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{basic} = 26.000$

Modification factor (Tension) $MF_t = \text{MIN}[0.55 + ((477 - f_s) / (120 \times (0.9 + (M / (b_w \times d^2))))), 2.0] = 2.000$

Modification factor (Compression) $MF_c = \text{MIN}[(1 + ((100 \times A_s'_{prov}) / (b_w \times d))) / (3 + (100 \times A_s'_{prov}) / (b_w \times d)), 1.5] = 1.100$

Maximum allowable span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{max} = (L / d)_{basic} \times MF_t \times MF_c = 57.183$

Actual span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{actual} = 9.774$

Deflection check: $(L / d)_{actual} \leq (L / d)_{max}$

Pass
Increase reinforcement if deflection fails : Not required

Shear Links - Critical

0.000 - 2.067 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Link Checks - Critical

Link utilization ratio $(A_{sv} / s_v)_{reqd} / (A_{sv} / s_v)_{prov} = 0.000$

Pass
 $(A_{sv} / s_v)_{prov} \geq (A_{svs} / s_{vs})_{min}$

Pass

Canopy Beam - 3 230x900 - Critical

Longitudinal Bars - Critical

Top: 0.000 - 1.186 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.250$

Provided tension bars: 2H20

Pass
Compression steel utilization ratio $A_s'_{reqd} / A_s'_{prov} = 0.000$

Provided compression bars: 2H16

Pass

Bottom: 0.000 - 2.373 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Tension steel utilization ratio $A_{st,reqd} / A_{s,prov} = 0.000$

Provided tension bars: 2H16

Pass
Compression steel utilization ratio $A_s'_{reqd} / A_s'_{prov} = 0.000$

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.3
Table 3.9

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.5
Table 3.10 equation 7

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.6
Table 3.11 equation 9

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.6

BS 8110-1:1997
Section 3.4.6.5

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Provided compression bars: 2H16

✓ Pass

Deflection Check - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Beam width $b_w = 230.0$ mm

Effective depth in region $d = 850.0$ mm

Clear span length $L = 2.258$ m

Span/effective depth $(L / d)_{basic} = 7.000$ ratio

BS 8110-1:1997

Section 3.4.6.3

Table 3.9

BS 8110-1:1997

Section 3.4.6.5

Table 3.10 equation

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Modification factor $MF_t = \text{MIN}[0.55 + ((477 - f_s) / (120 \times (0.9 + (M / (b_w \times d^2))))), 2.0] = 2.000$ (Tension)

Modification factor $MF_c = \text{MIN}[(1 + ((100 \times A_{s,prov}) / (b_w \times d))) / (3 + (100 \times A_{s,prov}) / (b_w \times d)), 1.5] = 1.064$ (Compression)

BS 8110-1:1997

Section 3.4.6.6

Table 3.11 equation

9

Maximum allowable span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{max} = (L / d)_{basic} \times MF_t \times MF_c = 14.898$

BS 8110-1:1997

Section 3.4.6.6

BS 8110-1:1997

Section 3.4.6.5

Actual span/effective depth ratio $(L / d)_{actual} = 2.656$

Deflection check: $(L / d)_{actual} \leq (L / d)_{max}$

✓ Pass

Increase reinforcement if deflection fails : Not required

Shear Links - Critical

0.000 - 0.593 - Critical

3D Building Analysis - Critical

1 Cb₁-1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI - Critical

Link Checks - Critical

Link utilization ratio $(A_{sv} / S_v)_{reqd} / (A_{sv} / S_v)_{prov} = 0.000$

✓ Pass

$(A_{sv} / S_v)_{prov} \geq (A_{sv} / S_v)_{nom}$

✓ Pass

Bending Moment Diagram, First-order linear

Major

	Project		Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos		Job Ref.		N5205
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Static Design Summary

Canopy Beam - 1 230x900 - Critical

Design summary bending top

Region	1	2
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	9.0 kNm	46.8 kNm
d	852.0 mm	850.0 mm
d'	48.0 mm	48.0 mm
K / K'	0.01	0.05
z	809.4 mm	807.5 mm
A _{s,reqd}	26 mm ²	133 mm ²
A _{sIT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _s ¹ _{reqd}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	26 mm ²	133 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	269 mm ²	269 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	402 mm ²	628 mm ²
Top bars	2H16	2H20
Deflection check	-	(L / d) _{actual} = 2.657 < 14.898

Design summary bending bottom

Region	1
Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	5.1 kNm
d	852.0 mm
d'	50.0 mm
K / K'	0.00
z	809.4 mm
A _{s,reqd}	15 mm ²
A _{sIT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²
A _s ¹ _{reqd}	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	15 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	269 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	402 mm ²
Bottom bars	2H16

Design summary shear and torsion

Region	Left	Right
Length	1.780 m	0.593 m
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
V	30.1 kN	68.1 kN
V _{max}	977.5 kN	977.5 kN
V _c	98.8 kN	98.8 kN
(A _{svs} / S _{vs}) _{reqd}	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m
(A _{sv} / S _v) _{prov}	785 mm ² /m	785 mm ² /m
T	0.00 kNm	0.00 kNm
T _{F,max}	977.5 kN	977.5 kN
T _F	0.0 kN	0.0 kN
(A _{svt} / S _{vt}) _{reqd}	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m
Links	2H10-200	2H10-200

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App'd by	N.C.O		Date		18/04/2024		

Canopy Beam - 2 230x900 - Critical

Design summary bending top

Region	1	2	3
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	51.8 kNm	0.0 kNm	66.6 kNm
d	850.0 mm	835.0 mm	850.0 mm
d'	77.5 mm	77.5 mm	77.5 mm
K / K'	0.05	0.00	0.06
z	807.5 mm	0.0 mm	807.5 mm
A _{s,reqd}	147 mm ²	0 mm ²	190 mm ²
A _{stT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{s'¹reqd}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	147 mm ²	0 mm ²	190 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	269 mm ²	0 mm ²	269 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	628 mm ²	942 mm ²	628 mm ²
Top bars	2H20	3H20	2H20

Design summary bending bottom

Region	1	2	3
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	62.2 kNm	199.0 kNm	53.0 kNm
d	822.5 mm	822.5 mm	822.5 mm
d'	50.0 mm	65.0 mm	50.0 mm
K / K'	0.06	0.20	0.05
z	781.4 mm	781.4 mm	781.4 mm
A _{s,reqd}	183 mm ²	585 mm ²	156 mm ²
A _{stT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{s'¹reqd}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	183 mm ²	585 mm ²	156 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	269 mm ²	269 mm ²	269 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	1963 mm ²	1963 mm ²	1963 mm ²
Bottom bars	4H25	4H25	4H25
Deflection check	-	(L / d) _{actual} = 9.774 < 57.183	-

Design summary shear and torsion

Region	Left	Centre	Right
Length	2.067 m	4.135 m	2.067 m
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
V	90.5 kN	83.1 kN	138.6 kN
V _{max}	945.9 kN	945.9 kN	945.9 kN
V _c	141.4 kN	141.4 kN	141.4 kN
(A _{svs} / S _{vs}) _{reqd}	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m
(A _{sv} / S _v) _{prov}	785 mm ² /m	785 mm ² /m	785 mm ² /m
T	0.00 kNm	0.00 kNm	0.00 kNm
T _{F,max}	945.9 kN	945.9 kN	945.9 kN
T _F	0.0 kN	0.0 kN	0.0 kN
(A _{svt} / S _{vt}) _{reqd}	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m
Links	2H10-200	2H10-200	2H10-200

Canopy Beam - 3 230x900 - Critical

	Project		Metropolitan Tower, Victoria Island, Lagos		Job Ref.		N5205
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	Adeola.Adeluwoye	10/07/2024	A.D.N	18/04/2024	N.C.O		18/04/2024

Design summary bending top

Region	1	2
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	55.2 kNm	16.0 kNm
d	850.0 mm	852.0 mm
d'	48.0 mm	48.0 mm
K / K'	0.05	0.02
z	807.5 mm	809.4 mm
A _{s,reqd}	157 mm ²	46 mm ²
A _{sIT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{s'} _{reqd}	0 mm ²	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	157 mm ²	46 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	269 mm ²	269 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	628 mm ²	402 mm ²
Top bars	2H20	2H16
Deflection check	(L / d) _{actual} = 2.656 < 14.898	-

Design summary bending bottom

Region	1
Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
M	0.0 kNm
d	852.0 mm
d'	50.0 mm
K / K'	0.00
z	0.0 mm
A _{s,reqd}	0 mm ²
A _{sIT,reqd,face}	0 mm ²
A _{s'} _{reqd}	0 mm ²
A _{st,reqd}	0 mm ²
A _{s,min,tens}	0 mm ²
A _{s,prov}	402 mm ²
Bottom bars	2H16

Design summary shear and torsion

Region	Left	Right
Length	0.593 m	1.780 m
Analysis	3D Building Analysis	3D Building Analysis
Combination	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI	1 Cb ₁ -1.4D+1.6I+1.6RI
V	31.3 kN	33.0 kN
V _{max}	977.5 kN	977.5 kN
V _c	98.8 kN	98.8 kN
(A _{svs} / S _{vs}) _{reqd}	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m
(A _{sv} / S _v) _{prov}	785 mm ² /m	785 mm ² /m
T	0.00 kNm	0.00 kNm
T _{F,max}	977.5 kN	977.5 kN
T _F	0.0 kN	0.0 kN
(A _{svt} / S _{vt}) _{reqd}	0 mm ² /m	0 mm ² /m
Links	2H10-200	2H10-200

COLUMN BASE PLATE DESIGN (BS5950-1:2000)

TEDDS calculation version 1.0.09

20 mm thick base plate

Base plate reference

SHS anchored directly to RC beam

Design forces and moments

Axial force

$F_c = 0.0$ kN

Bending moment

$M = 28.1$ kNm (about major axis)

Shear force

$F_v = 43.8$ kN

Column details

Column section

SHS 250x250x8.0 (Grade S275)

Depth

$D = 250.0$ mm

Breadth

$B = 250.0$ mm

Flange thickness

$T = 8.0$ mm

Web thickness

$t = 8.0$ mm

Design strength

$p_{yc} = 275$ N/mm²

Column flange to base plate weld

6 mm FW

Column web to base plate weld

6 mm FW

Baseplate details

Steel grade

S275

Depth

$D_p = 450$ mm

Breadth

$B_p = 450$ mm

Thickness

$t_p = 20$ mm

Design strength

$p_{yp} = 265$ N/mm²

Holding down bolt and anchor plate details

Total number of bolts

4 No. M16 Grade 4.6

Bolt spacing

$S_{bolt} = 200$ mm

Edge distance

$e_1 = 65$ mm

Anchor plate steel grade

S275

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Section Front Canopy - SHS sitting on RC Beam				Sheet no./rev. 2	
Calc. by AOA	Date 15/05/2024	Chk'd by ADN	Date	App'd by ATF	Date

Anchor plate dimension (square)	$b_{ap} = 100 \text{ mm}$
Anchor plate thickness	$t_{ap} = 20 \text{ mm}$
Design strength	$p_{yap} = 265 \text{ N/mm}^2$
Embedment to top of anchor plate	$E = 225 \text{ mm}$
Characteristic strength of concrete	$f_{cu} = 25 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Concrete compression force and bolt tension force

Plate overhang beyond face of flange	$L_1 = (D_p - D)/2 = 100.0 \text{ mm}$
Effective width of plate	$B_{pc} = \min(B_p, B + 2 \times L_1) = 450.0 \text{ mm}$
Distance from bolts to compression edge	$h = D_p - e_1 = 385 \text{ mm}$
Assuming a rectangular compression block of width b_{pc} , length x and intensity $0.6f_{cu}$ then:-	
From static equilibrium	$M = 0.6f_{cu}B_{pc}x(h-x/2) - F_c(h-D_p/2)$
Rearranging the quadratic equation	$0.3f_{cu}B_{pc}x^2 - 0.6f_{cu}B_{pc}hx + F_c(h-D_p/2) + M = 0$
Factor a	$a = 0.3 \times f_{cu} \times B_{pc} = 3375.0 \text{ N/mm}$
Factor b	$b = -0.6 \times f_{cu} \times B_{pc} \times h = -2598750.0 \text{ N}$
Constant c	$c = F_c \times (h-D_p/2) + M = 28070000.0 \text{ Nmm}$
Depth of compression block	$x = [-1.0 \times b - \sqrt{(b^2 - 4 \times a \times c)}] / (2 \times a) = 11.0 \text{ mm}$
Compression force in concrete	$C_f = 0.6 \times f_{cu} \times B_{pc} \times x = 74.0 \text{ kN}$
Tension force in bolts	$T_f = C_f - F_c = 74.0 \text{ kN}$

Therefore the bolts are in tension

Compression side bending

Moment in plate	$m_c = 0.6 \times f_{cu} \times x \times (L_1 - 0.8 \times S_{wf} - x/2) = 14747 \text{ Nmm/mm}$
Plate thickness required	$t_{pc} = \sqrt{(4 \times m_c / p_{yp})} = 14.9 \text{ mm}$

Tension side bending

Lever arm	$m = L_1 - e_1 - 0.8 \times S_{wf} = 30.2 \text{ mm}$
Moment in plate	$m_t = T_f \times m = 2233640 \text{ Nmm}$
Distance from bolt cl. to face of column	$L_f = L_1 - e_1 = 35.0 \text{ mm}$
Effective plate width	$B_{pt} = \min(B_p, S_{bolt} \times (N_{bolt}/2 - 1) + 2 \times L_f) = 270.0 \text{ mm}$
Plate thickness required	$t_{pt} = \sqrt{(4 \times m_t / (p_{yp} \times B_{pt}))} = 11.2 \text{ mm}$

Plate thickness

Plate thickness required	$t_{p_req} = \max(t_{pc}, t_{pt}) = 14.9 \text{ mm}$
Plate thickness provided	$t_p = 20 \text{ mm}$

PASS - Plate thickness provided is adequate (0.746)

Flange weld

Tension capacity of flange	$P_{tf} = B \times T \times p_{yc} = 550.0 \text{ kN}$
Force in tension flange	$F_{tf} = M / (D - T) - F_c \times (B \times T) / A = 116.0 \text{ kN}$
Flange weld design force	$F_f = \min(P_{tf}, \max(F_{tf}, 0 \text{ kN})) = 116.0 \text{ kN}$
Weld force per mm	$f_{wf} = F_f / B = 0.464 \text{ kN/mm}$
Transverse capacity of 6 mm fillet weld	$p_{wtf} = 1.155 \text{ kN/mm}$ (Cl. 6.8.7.3)

PASS - Flange weld capacity is adequate (0.402)

Longitudinal capacity of web weld

Weld force per mm	$f_{wwl} = F_f / (2 \times (D - 2 \times t)) = 0.094 \text{ kN/mm}$
Longitudinal capacity of 6 mm fillet weld	$p_{wwl} = 0.924 \text{ kN/mm}$ (Cl. 6.8.7.3)

PASS - Longitudinal capacity of web weld is adequate (0.101)

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Holding down bolts

Force per bolt	$F_{\text{bolt}} = (2 \times T_f) / N_{\text{bolt}} = 37.0 \text{ kN}$
Tensile area per bolt	$A_{t,b} = 157.0 \text{ mm}^2$
Tensile strength	$p_{t,b} = 240 \text{ N/mm}^2$
Tension capacity (cl.6.3.4.3)	$P_{t,b} = p_{t,b} \times A_{t,b} = 37.7 \text{ kN}$

PASS - Bolt capacity is adequate (0.981)

Anchor plates

Force per anchor plate	$F_{\text{ap}} = F_{\text{bolt}} = 37.0 \text{ kN}$
Bolt hole diameter in anchor plate	$d_h = 18 \text{ mm}$
Anchor plate bearing area	$A_{\text{ap}} = b_{\text{ap}}^2 - \pi \times d_h^2 / 4 = 9746 \text{ mm}^2$
Bearing capacity	$P_{\text{ap}} = 0.6 \times f_{\text{cu}} \times A_{\text{ap}} = 146.2 \text{ kN}$
Bearing pressure on anchor plate	$f_{\text{ap}} = F_{\text{ap}} / A_{\text{ap}} = 3.8 \text{ N/mm}^2$
Width of bolt head (across flats)	$d_{\text{bh}} = 24.0 \text{ mm}$
Maximum cantilever length	$l_{\text{ap}} = b_{\text{ap}} / 2 \times \sqrt{2} - d_{\text{bh}} / 2 = 58.7 \text{ mm}$
Bending moment in plate	$m_{\text{ap}} = f_{\text{ap}} \times l_{\text{ap}}^2 / 2 = 6.5 \text{ Nm/mm}$
Bending capacity	$m_{\text{cap}} = p_{\text{yap}} \times l_{\text{ap}}^2 / 4 = 26.5 \text{ Nm/mm}$

PASS - Anchor plate bearing capacity is adequate (0.253)

PASS - Anchor plate bending capacity is adequate (0.247)

Holding down bolt anchorage

Note - the following calculation to check the holding down bolt anchorage into the foundation assumes that the distance from the edge of an anchor plate to the nearest edge of the foundation is at least equal to the depth of embedment of the anchor plate.

Tension force to be resisted	$F_t = T_f = 74.0 \text{ kN}$
The clear distance between anchor plates is less than the embedment (E).	
Effective concrete plan area	$A_{\text{plan_eff}} = [S_{\text{bolt}} \times (N_{\text{bolt}} / 2 - 1) + b_{\text{ap}}] \times (b_{\text{ap}} + 2 \times E) + \pi \times E^2 + 2 \times b_{\text{ap}} \times E - (N_{\text{bolt}} / 2) \times b_{\text{ap}}^2$ $A_{\text{plan_eff}} = 349043 \text{ mm}^2$
For tension failure pull-out, effective tensile area	$A_{t_eff} = A_{\text{plan_eff}} = 349043 \text{ mm}^2$
Tensile strength of concrete	$p_t = 1.26 \text{ N/mm}^2$
Pull-out capacity of tension bolts	$P_t = p_t \times A_{t_eff} = 439.8 \text{ kN}$

PASS - Holding down bolt anchorage is adequate (0.168)

Shear transfer to concrete

Assumed coefficient of friction	$\mu = 0.30$
Available shear resistance	$P_v = C_f \times \mu = 22 \text{ kN}$

WARNING - Friction alone is not adequate to resist applied shear force
Additional design measures required which are not covered by this calculation

COLUMN BASE PLATE DESIGN (BS5950-1:2000)

TEDDS calculation version 1.0.09

Design forces and moments

Axial force	$F_c = 398.1$ kN (Compression)
Bending moment	$M = 16.5$ kNm (about major axis)
Shear force	$F_v = 10.1$ kN

Column details

Column section	SHS 180x180x6.3 (Grade S275)
Depth	$D = 180.0$ mm
Breadth	$B = 180.0$ mm
Flange thickness	$T = 6.3$ mm
Web thickness	$t = 6.3$ mm
Design strength	$p_{yc} = 275$ N/mm ²
Column flange to base plate weld	6 mm FW
Column web to base plate weld	6 mm FW

Baseplate details

Steel grade	S275
Depth	$D_p = 400$ mm
Breadth	$B_p = 400$ mm
Thickness	$t_p = 20$ mm
Design strength	$p_{yp} = 265$ N/mm ²

Holding down bolt and anchor plate details

Total number of bolts	4 No. M16 Grade 4.6
Bolt spacing	$S_{bolt} = 160$ mm
Edge distance	$e_1 = 70$ mm
Anchor plate steel grade	S275

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Section Front Canopy - Main CHS section directly on GF slab				Sheet no./rev. 2	
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Anchor plate dimension (square)	$b_{ap} = 100 \text{ mm}$
Anchor plate thickness	$t_{ap} = 20 \text{ mm}$
Design strength	$p_{yap} = 265 \text{ N/mm}^2$
Embedment to top of anchor plate	$E = 350 \text{ mm}$
Characteristic strength of concrete	$f_{cu} = 25 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Concrete compression force and bolt tension force

Plate overhang beyond face of flange	$L_1 = (D_p - D)/2 = 110.0 \text{ mm}$
Effective width of plate	$B_{pc} = \min(B_p, B + 2 \times L_1) = 400.0 \text{ mm}$
Distance from bolts to compression edge	$h = D_p - e_t = 330 \text{ mm}$
Assuming a rectangular compression block of width b_{pc} , length x and intensity $0.6f_{cu}$ then:-	
From static equilibrium	$M = 0.6f_{cu}B_{pc}x(h-x/2) - F_c(h-D_p/2)$
Rearranging the quadratic equation	$0.3f_{cu}B_{pc}x^2 - 0.6f_{cu}B_{pc}hx + F_c(h-D_p/2) + M = 0$
Factor a	$a = 0.3 \times f_{cu} \times B_{pc} = 3000.0 \text{ N/mm}$
Factor b	$b = -0.6 \times f_{cu} \times B_{pc} \times h = -1980000.0 \text{ N}$
Constant c	$c = F_c \times (h-D_p/2) + M = 68255600.0 \text{ Nmm}$
Depth of compression block	$x = [-1.0 \times b - \sqrt{(b^2 - 4 \times a \times c)}] / (2 \times a) = 36.5 \text{ mm}$
Compression force in concrete	$C_f = 0.6 \times f_{cu} \times B_{pc} \times x = 218.9 \text{ kN}$
Tension force in bolts	$T_f = C_f - F_c = -179.2 \text{ kN}$

Therefore the bolts are not in tension - Recalculate depth of compression block

Actual compression force in concrete	$C_f = F_c = 398 \text{ kN}$
Actual force in bolts	$T_f = 0 \text{ kN}$
Eccentricity of compression force	$e = M/F_c = 41.4 \text{ mm}$
Depth of compression block	$x = 2 \times (D_p/2 - e) = 317.1 \text{ mm}$
Stress in concrete	$f_c = F_c / (B_{pc} \times x) = 3.1 \text{ N/mm}^2$

Compression side bending

Moment in plate	$m_c = f_c \times (L_1 - 0.8 \times S_{wt})^2 / 2 = 17368 \text{ Nmm/mm}$
Plate thickness required	$t_{pc} = \sqrt{(4 \times m_c / p_{yp})} = 16.2 \text{ mm}$

Plate thickness

Plate thickness required	$t_{p_req} = t_{pc} = 16.2 \text{ mm}$
Plate thickness provided	$t_p = 20 \text{ mm}$

PASS - Plate thickness provided is adequate (0.810)

Flange weld

Tension capacity of flange	$P_{tf} = B \times T \times p_{yc} = 311.9 \text{ kN}$
Force in tension flange	$F_{tf} = M / (D - T) - F_c \times (B \times T) / A = -9.2 \text{ kN}$
Flange weld design force	$F_f = \min(P_{tf}, \max(F_{tf}, 0 \text{ kN})) = 0.0 \text{ kN}$
Weld force per mm	$f_{wf} = F_f / B = 0.000 \text{ kN/mm}$
Transverse capacity of 6 mm fillet weld	$p_{wf} = 1.155 \text{ kN/mm}$ (Cl. 6.8.7.3)

PASS - Flange weld capacity is adequate (0.000)

Longitudinal capacity of web weld

Weld force per mm	$f_{wwl} = F_v / (2 \times (D - 2 \times t)) = 0.030 \text{ kN/mm}$
Longitudinal capacity of 6 mm fillet weld	$p_{wwl} = 0.924 \text{ kN/mm}$ (Cl. 6.8.7.3)

PASS - Longitudinal capacity of web weld is adequate (0.033)

Project Metropolitan Tower				Job Ref. N5205	
Section Front Canopy - Main CHS section directly on GF slab				Sheet no./rev. 3	
Calc. by AOA	Date 15/05/2024	Chk'd by ADN	Date	App'd by ATF	Date

Shear transfer to concrete

Assumed coefficient of friction

$$\mu = 0.30$$

Available shear resistance

$$P_v = C_f \times \mu = \mathbf{119 \text{ kN}}$$

PASS - Frictional shear capacity is adequate (0.085)

RC PILE CAP DESIGN (BS8110:PART1:1997)

TEDDS calculation version 2.0.10

Pile Cap Design – Truss Method

Design Input - 3 Piles - With Eccentricity

Number of piles	N = 3
ULS axial load	$F_{uls} = 34137.7$ kN
Characteristic axial load	$F_{char} = 23382.0$ kN
Pile diameter	$\phi = 1300.0$ mm
Pile spacing	s = 3900.0 mm
Eccentricity from centroid of pile cap	$e_x = 200.0$ mm
Characteristic load in pile, ϕ_1	$F_{char_pile_1} = F_{char} \times (\cos(30)/3 \times s + e_x) / (\cos(30) \times s) = 9178.6$ kN
Characteristic load in pile, ϕ_2	$F_{char_pile_2} = F_{char} \times (\tan(30) \times s - e_x) / (\cos(30) \times s) / 2 = 7101.7$ kN
Characteristic load in pile, ϕ_3	$F_{char_pile_3} = F_{char} \times (\tan(30) \times s - e_x) / (\cos(30) \times s) / 2 = 7101.7$ kN
Pile cap overhang	e = 200 mm
Overall length of pile cap	$L = \sin(60) \times s + \phi + 2 \times e = 5077$ mm
Overall width of pile cap	b = s + $\phi + 2 \times e = 5600$ mm
Width at pile parallel to length, L	$w_1 = \phi + 2 \times e = 1700$ mm
Width at pile parallel to overall width, b	$w_2 = \phi + 2 \times e = 1700$ mm
Overall height of pile cap	h = 2300 mm
Diagonal length of sides	$L_{side_diag} = \sqrt{((L-w_1)^2 + ((b-w_2)/2)^2)} = 3900$ mm
Dimension x of loaded area	x = 400 mm
Dimension y of loaded area	y = 1800 mm

Cover

Concrete grade	$f_{cu} = 40.0$ N/mm ²
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Project METROPOLITAN TOWERS				Job Ref. N5205	
Section PILE CAP FOUNDATION DESIGN				Sheet no./rev. 2 00	
Calc. by BAE	Date 10/28/2022	Chk'd by ADN	Date	App'd by	Date

Nominal cover $C_{nom} = 40$ mm
 Tension bar diameter $D_t = 32$ mm
 Link bar diameter $L_{dia} = 12$ mm
 Depth to tension steel $d = h - C_{nom} - L_{dia} - D_t/2 = 2232$ mm

Pile Cap Forces

Maximum compression within pile cap $F_c = \max(F_{c1}, F_{c2}, F_{c3}) = 18202.0$ kN
 Maximum tension within pile cap $F_t = \max(F_{t1}, F_{t2}, F_{t3}) = 7111.8$ kN

Compression In Pile Cap - Suggested Additional Check

Check compression diagonal as an unreinforced column, using a core equivalent to pile diameter

Compressive force in pile cap $P_c = 0.4 \times f_{cu} \times \pi \times \phi^2/4 = 21237.2$ kN

PASS Compression
 Cl. 3.8.4.3

Tension In One Truss Member

Characteristic strength of reinforcement $f_y = 500$ N/mm²
 Partial safety factor for strength of steel $\gamma_{ms} = 1.15$
 Req'd area of reinf't (in one truss member) $A_{s_req} = F_t / (1/\gamma_{ms} \times f_y) = 16357$ mm²
 Provided area of reinf't (in one truss member) $A_{s_prov} = A_{st} = 16889$ mm²
 Tension capacity of truss member $P_t = (1/\gamma_{ms} \times f_y) \times A_{s_prov} = 7343.1$ kN

PASS Tension
 Cl. 3.11.4.2

Max / Min Areas of Reinforcement - Considering A Strip Of Cap

Minimum required area of steel $A_{st_min} = k_t \times A_c = 1495$ mm²
 Maximum allowable area of steel $A_{st_max} = 4\% \times A_c = 46000$ mm²

Area of tension steel provided OK
 Cl. 3.12.6 & Table 3.25

Beam Shear

Check shear stress on the sections at distance $\phi / 5$ inside face of piles.

Cl. 3.11.4.3 & fig. 3.23

Applied shear stress

$v_1 = V_1 / (b_{v1} \times d) = 1.54$ N/mm²
 $v_2 = V_2 / (b_{v2} \times d) = 1.57$ N/mm²
 $v_3 = V_3 / (b_{v3} \times d) = 1.57$ N/mm²
 Allowable shear stress $v_{allowable} = \min((0.8 \text{ N}^{1/2}/\text{mm}) \times \sqrt{f_{cu}}, 5 \text{ N/mm}^2) = 5.00$ N/mm²

Shear stress - OK
 Cl. 3.4.5.2

Design concrete shear strength - Pile 1

Shear stress - Table 3.8

$$v_{c_251} = 0.79 \times r_1^{1/3} \times \max(0.67, (400 \text{ mm}/d)^{1/4}) \times 1.0 \text{ N/mm}^2 / 1.25 = 0.31 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Adopting shear enhancement rules to Cl. 3.4.5.8 and fig. 3.5

$$v_{c1} = v_{c_251} \times (\min(f_{cu}, 40 \text{ N/mm}^2) / 25 \text{ N/mm}^2)^{1/3} = 0.36 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

$$a_{v_1} = \min(2 \times d, \max((s/\sqrt{3}) - \phi/2 + \phi/5 - x/2 - e_x), 0.1 \text{ mm})) = 1462 \text{ mm}$$

$$v_{c_enh_1} = \min(v_{allowable}, 2 \times d \times v_{c1} / a_{v_1}) = 1.10 \text{ N/mm}^2$$

Concrete shear stress - NOT OK, provide DESIGNED links at Pile 1

Project METROPOLITAN TOWERS				Job Ref. N5205	
Section PILE CAP FOUNDATION DESIGN				Sheet no./rev. 3 00	
Calc. by BAE	Date 10/28/2022	Chk'd by ADN	Date	App'd by	Date

Table 3.16

Design concrete shear strength - Piles 2 and 3

Shear stress - Table 3.8

$$V_{c,252} = 0.79 \times r_2^{1/3} \times \max(0.67, (400 \text{ mm/d})^{1/4}) \times 1.0 \text{ N/mm}^2 / 1.25 = \mathbf{0.34 \text{ N/mm}^2}$$

$$V_{c3} = V_{c2} = V_{c,252} \times (\min(f_{cu}, 40 \text{ N/mm}^2) / 25 \text{ N/mm}^2)^{1/3} = \mathbf{0.40 \text{ N/mm}^2}$$

$$a_{v,2} = \min(2 \times d, \max((s/2 / \cos(\theta_{23}) - \phi/2 + \phi/5 - y/2), 0.1 \text{ mm})) = \mathbf{1068 \text{ mm}}$$

$$V_{c,enh,3} = V_{c,enh,2} = 2 \times d \times V_{c2} / a_{v,2} = \mathbf{1.66 \text{ N/mm}^2}$$

Concrete shear strength - OK, no links reqd. at Piles 2 and 3

Table 3.16

Note: If no links are provided, the bond strengths for **PLAIN** bars must be used in calculations for anchorage and lap lengths.

Cl. 3.12.8.3

Design Shear Links – Pile 1

Total area of shear reinforcement required within middle three-quarters of $a_{v,1}$:

$$\Sigma A_{sv,reqd,1} = a_{v,1} \times b_{v1} \times \max(0.4 \text{ N/mm}^2, (v_1 - V_{c,enh,1})) / (f_{yv} / \gamma_{ms}) = \mathbf{5719 \text{ mm}^2}$$

Hence

$$A_{sv,to,sv,reqd,1} = \Sigma A_{sv,reqd,1} / (0.75 \times a_{v,1}) = \mathbf{5.22 \text{ mm}}$$

Maximum allowable spacing of links

$$s_{v,max} = 0.75 \times d = \mathbf{1674 \text{ mm}}$$

$$A_{sv,to,sv,1} = \mathbf{9.383 \text{ mm}}$$

Link spacing

$$s_{v1} = \mathbf{150 \text{ mm}}$$

Link diameter

$$L_{dia1} = \mathbf{16 \text{ mm}}$$

No of legs in each group

$$L_{n1} = \mathbf{7}$$

Shear Links - PASS

Local Shear At Concentrated Loads (Cl 3.7.7)

Total length of inner perim. at edge of loaded area $u_0 = 2 \times (x + y) = \mathbf{4400 \text{ mm}}$

Assumed average depth to tension steel $d_{av} = d - D_t = \mathbf{2200 \text{ mm}}$

Max shear effective across perimeter $V_p = F_{uls} = \mathbf{34137.7 \text{ kN}}$

Stress around loaded area $v_{max} = V_p / (u_0 \times d_{av}) = \mathbf{3.53 \text{ N/mm}^2}$

Allowable shear stress $v_{allowable} = \min((0.8 \text{ N}^{1/2}/\text{mm}) \times \sqrt{f_{cu}}, 5 \text{ N/mm}^2) = \mathbf{5.00 \text{ N/mm}^2}$

Shear stress - OK

Cl. 3.4.5.2

Clear Distance Between Bars In Tension (Cl 3.12.11.2.4)

Maximum / Minimum allowable clear distances between tension bars considering a strip of cap

Actual bar spacing

$$\text{spacing}_{bars} = \max(0 \text{ mm}, (b_{ccs} - n_{surfaces} \times (C_{adopt} + L_{dia}) - D_t) / (L_{nt} - 1) - D_t) = \mathbf{11 \text{ mm}}$$

Maximum allowable spacing of bars $\text{spacing}_{max} = \min((47000 \text{ N/mm}) / f_s, 300 \text{ mm}) = \mathbf{146 \text{ mm}}$

Minimum required spacing of bars $\text{spacing}_{min} = h_{agg} + 5 \text{ mm} = \mathbf{25 \text{ mm}}$

Less than minimum spacing - FAIL

Clear Distance Between Face Of Beam And Tension Bars (Cl 3.12.11.2.5)

Distance to face of beam $Dist_{edge} = C_{adopt} + L_{dia} + D_t/2 = \mathbf{68 \text{ mm}}$

Design service stress in reinforcement $f_s = 2 \times f_y \times A_{s,req} / (3 \times A_{s,prov} \times \beta_b) = \mathbf{322.8 \text{ N/mm}^2}$

Max allowable clear spacing $\text{Spacing}_{max} = \min((47000 \text{ N/mm}) / f_s, 300 \text{ mm}) = \mathbf{146 \text{ mm}}$

Max distance to face of beam $Dist_{max} = \text{Spacing}_{max} / 2 = \mathbf{73 \text{ mm}}$

Max distance to beam edge check - OK

Anchorage Of Tension Steel

Anchorage factor $\phi_{factor} = \mathbf{35}$

Type of lap length	lap_type = "tens_lap"
Type of reinforcement	reft_type = "def2_fy500"
Minimum radius	r _{bar} = 112 mm
Minimum end projection	P _{bar} = 305 mm
Minimum anchorage length or lap length req'd	L _{table 3.27} = φ _{factor} × D _t = 1120 mm
Check anchorage length to cl. 3.12.9.4 (b)	L _{cl. 3.12.9.4} = 12 × D _t + d/2 = 1500 mm
Required minimum effective anchorage length	L _a = max(L _{table 3.27} , L _{cl. 3.12.9.4}) = 1500 mm

Check minimum radius required on bend

Note that the bars must extend at least 4D past the bend

Force per bar at bend	F _{bt} = F _t / L _{nt} = 338.7 kN
Edge bar centres	S _{ext} = C _{adopt} + D _t = 72 mm
Edge maximum allowable bearing stress	f _{bt_max_ext} = 2 × f _{cu} / (1 + 2×(D _t / S _{ext})) = 42.35 N/mm²
Internal bar centres	S _{int} = spacing _{bars} + D _t = 43 mm
Internal maximum allowable bearing stress	f _{bt_max_int} = 2 × f _{cu} / (1 + 2×(D _t / S _{int})) = 32.24 N/mm²
Design max allowable bearing stress	f _{bt_max} = min(f _{bt_max_ext} , f _{bt_max_int}) = 32.24 N/mm²
Minimum radius required	r _{min} = max(r _{bar} , F _{bt} / (f _{bt_max} × D _t)) = 328.3 mm

Minimum radius of bend required = 328 mm

Project **METROPOLITAN TOWERS**
 Client **QUANTUM LUXURY PROPERTIES**
 Location **BESIDE CIVIC CENTRE OZUMBA**

Reinforced Concrete Council

Made by BAE	Date 10-Nov-22	Page 1
Checked -	Revision -	Job No N5205

PILECAP DESIGN to BS 8110:1997

5 Pile Cap

Originated from RCC82.xls v β5 on CD

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DIMENSIONS mm

COLUMN

→ = 1800
 ↑ = 400

PILECAP

A = 900
 B = 2500
 C = 3900
 D = 1250
 E = 1950
 Depth H = 1500

Pile Ø = 1000
 in spacing = 1300
 Tolerance = 0

PLOT (to scale)

COLUMN ACTIONS kN, kNm characteristic

	DEAD	IMPOSED	WIND
Axial (kN)	<u>17536.5</u>	<u>5845.5</u>	
Mx (kNm)			
My (kNm)			
Hx (kN)			
Hy (kN)			

STATUS **VALID DESIGN**

PILE REACTIONS kN

	PILE 1	PILE 2	PILE 3	PILE 4	PILE 5
Gk + Qk	4849.9	4849.9	4849.9	4849.9	4849.9
Gk + Qk + Wk	4849.9	4849.9	4849.9	4849.9	4849.9

REINFORCEMENT

EW(1/3-2/4) M = 4,916.6 kNm, b = 5,700 mm
 d = 1,397.5 mm, As = 8,453 mm²
23 T25 B2 = 11,290 mm²

V = 14,047.4 kN, bv = 5,700 mm
 v = 1.763 N/mm², (v-vc)b = 3,589 N/mm
23 Legs T16 @ 300 LINKS = 6,753 N/mm

NS(1/2-3/4) M = 24,583.0 kNm, b = 4,300 mm
 d = 1,430.0 mm, As = 42,879 mm²
35 T40 B1 = 43,982 mm²

V = 14,047.4 kN, bv = 4,300 mm
 v = 2.285 N/mm², (v-vc)b = 4,896 N/mm

Project	Metropolitan Tower		ARUP		
Client	Quantum Luxury Properties LTD		Made by	Date	Page
Location	Generator House	A to B: 1 to 2	ADN	15-Jun-2023	1
2-WAY SPANNING INSITU CONCRETE SLABS to BS 8110:1997 (Table 3.14)			Checked	Revision	Job No
<small>Originated from RCC94.xls v2.1 © 1999-2003 BCA for RCC</small>			ADN	-	N5205

DIMENSIONS short span, lx m 5.83 long span, ly m 8.00 h mm 175 Top cover mm 30 Btm cover mm 30		MATERIALS fcu N/mm ² 30 γ _c = 1.50 fy N/mm ² 460 γ _s = 1.05 Density kN/m ³ 23.6 (Normal weight concrete)		STATUS VALID DESIGN	
LOADING characteristic Self weight kN/m ² 4.13 Extra dead kN/m ² 2.10 Total Dead, gk kN/m ² 6.23 Imposed, qk kN/m ² 1.50 Design load, n kN/m ² 11.12		EDGE CONDITIONS Edge 1 C C = Continuous Edge 2 d D = Discontinuous Edge 3 C Edge 4 d			
		γ _f = 1.40 γ _f = 1.60		See Figure 3.8 and clauses 3.5.3.5-6	

MAIN STEEL	SHORT SPAN x	LONG SPAN y	EDGE 1	EDGE 2	EDGE 3	EDGE 4	Reference
	Continuous	Free	Continuous	Free	Continuous	Free	
β _s	0.044	0.034	0.059	0.000	0.059	0.000	BS8110
M kNm/m	16.7	12.9	22.3	0.0	22.3	0.0	Table 3.14
d mm	140.0	130.0	140.0	130.0	140.0	130.0	
k'	0.156	0.156	0.156	0.156	0.156	0.156	
k	0.028	0.025	0.038	0.000	0.038	0.000	3.4.4.4
Z mm	133.0	123.5	133.0	123.5	133.0	123.5	
As req mm ² /m	287	238	383	0	383	0	
As min mm ² /m	228	228	228	228	228	228	Table 3.25
As deflection mm ² /m	345	285	~	~	~	~	
Ø mm	10	10	10	10	10	10	
Layer	B 1	B 2	T 1	T 2	T 1	T 2	
@ mm	225	275	200	325	200	325	
As prov mm ² /m	349	286	393	242	393	242	
= %	0.249	0.220	0.280	0.186	0.280	0.186	%
S max mm	430	400	430	400	430	400	Clause
Subclause	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	(a)	3.12.11.2.7
DEFLECTION							
fs	252	255	299	0	299	0	Eqn 8
Mod factor	1.617						Eqn 7
Perm L/d	42.04	Actual L/d	41.64	Asx enhanced 20.0% for deflection control			Table 3.10

TORSION STEEL Ø mm 10 As req mm ² /m As prov T mm ² /m Additional As T req mm ² As prov B mm ² /m	BOTH EDGES DISCONTINUOUS		ONE EDGE DISCONTINUOUS		3.5.3.5
	X	Y	X	Y	
		228		228	
	5000	5000	393	242	
	0	0	0	0	
	349	286	349	286	

Bottom steel not curtailed in edge strips at free edges

SUPPORT REACTIONS (kN/m char uno) (See Figure 3.10)					Sum β _{vx} = 0.954 Sum β _{vy} = 0.520	Table 3.15
	EDGE 1	EDGE 2	EDGE 3	EDGE 4		equations 19 & 20
	1, A-B	B, 2-1	2, A-B	A, 2-1		
β _v	0.477	0.260	0.477	0.260		
Dead kN/m	17.33	9.44	17.33	9.44		
Imposed kN/m	4.17	2.27	4.17	2.27		
Vs kN/m	30.9	16.9	30.9	16.9		

OUTPUT/SUMMARY						
PROVIDE MAIN STEEL	SHORT SPAN	LONG SPAN	EDGE 1	EDGE 2	EDGE 3	EDGE 4
	T10 @ 225 B1	T10 @ 275 B2	T10 @ 200 T1	T10 @ 325 T2	T10 @ 200 T1	T10 @ 325 T2
ADDITIONAL TORSION STEEL X direction Y direction	CORNER 1	CORNER 2	CORNER 3	CORNER 4		
	A1	B1	B2	A2	<i>placed in edge strips</i>	

CHECKS Lx > Ly OK	BAR Ø < COVER OK	SINGLY REINFORCED OK	MIN SPACING OK	MAX SPACING OK	DEFLECTION OK	GLOBAL STATUS VALID DESIGN
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Project METROPOLITAN TOWER
 Client QUANTUM LUXURY PROPERTIES
 Location STAIRCASE TYPE 1 (BASEMENT - P.H LEV 2)
 REINFORCED CONCRETE STAIRCASES to BS 8110:1997
 Originated from RCC72.xls v2.1 on CD © 1999-2003 BCA for RCC

REINFORCED CONCRETE COUNCIL

Made by AOA	Date 10-Nov-22	Page 2
Checked A.D.N	Revision -	Job No N5205

LANDING 1 +1.500 m

h = 175 mm L = 3.270 m
 Self wt 4.20 n1 = 17.09/1.34 = 12.80 kN/m²
 Finishes 1.80 n2 = 23.62/1.34 = 17.69 kN/m²
 6.00 kN/m² na = 1.4x6.00+1.6x3.0 = 13.20 kN/m²

M = 44.25 x 1.516 - 15.17 - 18.14 = 33.77 kNm/m d = 144 mm K = 0.0543
 As = 764 mm² PROVIDE 7 T12 @ 200 B = 792 mm² L/d = 22.708 < 22.937 allowed

As increased by 2.4 % for deflection

OK

FLIGHT 3

Waist = 175 mm a = 2.800 m b = 0.668 m c = 0.860 m
 L = 4.328 m
 Waist 4.88
 Steps 1.99
 Finishes 1.80
 8.67 kN/m² n3 = 16.94 kN/m²

M = 24.77 x (2.130 - 0.731) = 34.65 kNm/m d = 144 mm K = 0.0557
 As = 806 mm² PROVIDE 12 T12 @ 110 B = 1357 mm² L/d = 30.052 < 30.117 allowed

As increased by 67.5 % for deflection

OK

LANDING 2 +3.000 m

h = 175 mm L = 3.270 m
 Self wt 4.20 n3 = 13.18 kN/m²
 Finishes 1.80 n2 = 12.56 kN/m²
 6.00 kN/m² nb = 13.20 kN/m²

M = 39.44 x 1.620 - 17.32 - 15.39 = 31.18 kNm/m d = 144 mm K = 0.0501
 As = 701 mm² PROVIDE 8 T12 @ 230 B = 905 mm² L/d = 22.708 < 22.842 allowed

OK

FLIGHT 4

Waist = 175 mm a = 2.800 m b = 0.668 m c = 0.860 m
 L = 4.328 m
 Waist 4.88
 Steps 1.99
 Finishes 1.80
 8.67 kN/m² n4 = 16.94 kN/m²

M = 24.77 x (2.130 - 0.731) = 34.65 kNm/m d = 144 mm K = 0.0557
 As = 806 mm² PROVIDE 12 T12 @ 110 B = 1357 mm² L/d = 30.052 < 30.117 allowed

As increased by 67.5 % for deflection

OK

LANDING 3 +4.825 m

h = 175 mm L = 3.270 m
 Self wt 4.20 n3 = 18.56 kN/m²
 Finishes 1.80 n4 = 18.56 kN/m²
 6.00 kN/m² nc = 13.20 kN/m²

M = 47.01 x 1.635 - 17.64 - 22.05 = 37.16 kNm/m d = 144 mm K = 0.0597
 As = 847 mm² PROVIDE 8 T12 @ 170 B = 905 mm² L/d = 22.708 < 22.763 allowed

As increased by 6.5 % for deflection

OK

Project **METROPOLITAN TOWER**
 Client **QUANTUM LUXURY PROPERTIES**
 Location **STARI CASE TYPE 2 (DUPLD LOWEFLIGHT**
 STAIR FLIGHTS AND LANDINGS to BS 8110:1997
 Originated from **RCC71.xls** v2.1 on CD © 1999-2003 BCA for RCC

REINFORCED CONCRETE COUNCIL

Made by A.O.A	Date 10-Nov-22	Page 1
Checked A.D.N	Revision -	Job No N5205

MATERIALS

fcu	30	N/mm ²	γ_m	1.5	concrete	Min bar $\varnothing =$ 12
fy	460	N/mm ²	γ_m	1.05	steel	Max bar $\varnothing =$ 12
h agg	20	mm	Density	24	kN/m ³	Nominal top steel ? Y
Cover	20	mm	<i>(Normal weight concrete)</i>			

DIMENSIONS

a =	1280	mm	landing A h =	150
b =	2100	mm	flight waist =	150
c =	200	mm	landing B h =	150
d =	0	mm		
e =	0	mm		
Going =	300	mm	L =	3580
Rise =	1161	mm total		7 treads
Rise =	165.9	mm each step	Rake =	28.94 °

Sectional Elevation

LOADING

Imposed	3.00	kN/m ²
Flight finishes	1.50	kN/m ²
Landing finishes	12.00	kN/m ²

DESIGN

LANDING A, $g_k = 3.60 + 12.00 = 15.60$ kN/m ²	$n = 1.4 \times 15.60 + 1.6 \times 3.0 = 26.64$ kN/m ²
FLIGHT, $g_k = 6.10 + 1.50 = 7.60$ kN/m ²	$n = 1.4 \times 7.60 + 1.6 \times 3.0 = 15.45$ kN/m ²
LANDING C, $g_k = 3.60 + 12.00 = 15.60$ kN/m ²	$n = 1.4 \times 15.60 + 1.6 \times 3.0 = 26.64$ kN/m ²

Zero shear is at $1.28 + (39.48 - 34.10) / 15.45 = 1.628$ m from left

$$M = 39.48 \times 1.628 - 34.10 \times 0.988 - 15.45 \times 0.348^2 / 2 = 29.64 \text{ kNm/m}$$

$$d = 150 - 20 - 6 = 124 \text{ mm}$$

$$K = 0.0643$$

$$A_s = 591 \text{ mm}^2/\text{m}$$

PROVIDE **T12 @ 120 B = 942 mm²/m**

Enhanced by 55.5 % for deflection

T12 @ 575 T in span

$$L/d = 3,580 / 124 = 28.871 < 20.0 \times 1.388 \times 1.050 = 29.164 \text{ allowed}$$

OK

Project **METROPOLITAN TOWER**
 Client **QUANTUM LUXURY PROPERTIES**
 Location **BASEMENT TO GROUND FLOOR (T 3) FLIGHT**
 STAIR FLIGHTS AND LANDINGS to BS 8110:1997
 Originated from **RCC71.xls** v2.1 on CD © 1999-2003 BCA for RCC

REINFORCED CONCRETE COUNCIL

Made by A.O.A	Date 10-Nov-22	Page 1
Checked A.D.N	Revision -	Job No N5205

MATERIALS

fcu	30	N/mm ²	γ_m	1.5	concrete	Min bar $\varnothing =$ 12
fy	460	N/mm ²	γ_m	1.05	steel	Max bar $\varnothing =$ 12
h agg	20	mm	Density	24	kN/m ³	Nominal top steel ? Y
Cover	20	mm	<i>(Normal weight concrete)</i>			

DIMENSIONS

a =	1200	mm	landing A h =	150
b =	2400	mm	flight waist =	150
c =	300	mm	landing B h =	150
d =	0	mm		
e =	0	mm		
Going =	300	mm	L =	3900
Rise =	1500	mm total		8 treads
Rise =	166.7	mm each step		Rake = 29.06 °

Sectional Elevation

LOADING

Imposed	3.00	kN/m ²
Flight finishes	1.50	kN/m ²
Landing finishes	1.50	kN/m ²

DESIGN

LANDING A, $g_k = 3.60 + 1.50 = 5.10$ kN/m ²	$n = 1.4 \times 5.10 + 1.6 \times 3.0 = 11.94$ kN/m ²
FLIGHT, $g_k = 6.12 + 1.50 = 7.62$ kN/m ²	$n = 1.4 \times 7.62 + 1.6 \times 3.0 = 15.47$ kN/m ²
LANDING C, $g_k = 3.60 + 1.50 = 5.10$ kN/m ²	$n = 1.4 \times 5.10 + 1.6 \times 3.0 = 11.94$ kN/m ²

Zero shear is at $1.2 + (26.54 - 14.33) / 15.47 = 1.989$ m from left

$$M = 26.54 \times 1.989 - 14.33 \times 1.389 - 15.47 \times 0.789^2 / 2 = 28.07 \text{ kNm/m}$$

$$d = 150 - 20 - 6 = 124 \text{ mm} \quad K = 0.0608 \quad A_s = 557 \text{ mm}^2/\text{m}$$

PROVIDE T12 @ 150 B = 754 mm²/m

Enhanced by 32.7 % for deflection **T12 @ 575 T in span**

$$L/d = 3,900 / 124 = 31.452 < 23.0 \times 1.315 \times 1.050 = 31.772 \text{ allowed}$$

OK

APPENDIX B - DESIGN DRAWINGS

Type	Unit Mass [kg/m]	Total Length [m]	Total Mass [kg]
H8	0.395	22.100	8.73
H16	1.579	10.900	17.21
H20	2.466	11.000	27.13
Grand Total			53.07

Mark	Type	Quantity	Length [mm]	Total Length [m]	Shape	Members
8	H8	17	1300.0	22.100	51	230 X 450 Beam
9	H16	2	5450.0	10.900	21	230 X 450 Beam
10	H20	2	5500.0	11.000	21	230 X 450 Beam

230 X 450 Beam - 1 (230x450)

230 x 230 Column

230 x 230 Column B-B

Type	Unit Mass (kg/m)	Total Length [m]	Total Mass [kg]
H10	0.616	36.800	22.67
H16	1.579	14.200	22.42
H25	3.854	40.800	157.24
Grand Total			202.33

Mark	Type	Quantity	Length [mm]	Total Length [m]	Shape	Members
2	H25	4	2425.0	9.700	34	230 x 230 Column
3	H25	4	7775.0	31.100	26	230 x 230 Column
4	H16	4	3550.0	14.200	11	230 x 230 Column
5	H10	46	800.0	36.800	51	230 x 230 Column

230 x 230 Column A-A

Pad footing

Type	Unit Mass [kg/m]	Total Length [m]	Total Mass [kg]
H16	1.579	53.268	84.11
Grand Total			84.11

2 FRONT CANOPY
1 : 50

FRONT CANOPY DETAILS 'C'

SCALE 1:10

3 - 3
SCALE 1:10

DETAIL 'B'
(FRONT CANOPY)

7No THUS
(SCALE 1:10)

6 - 6
(SCALE 1:10)

FROM FLOOR 1 [LEVEL +3.815] – 2ND HALF LANDING (2 NOS. THUS) SCALE:1:50

FROM 2ND HALF LANDING – L1/F [LEVEL +9.400] (2 NOS. THUS) SCALE:1:50

KEY PLAN (FLIGHT 3, 4, 5 & 6) (2 NOS. THUS)

- NOTES
1. DIMENSIONS TO BE CHECKED ON SITE
 2. DIMENSIONS ARE TO BE TAKEN TO CENTER LINES, OF STRUCTURAL SURFACES AND JOINT LOCATIONS
 3. FINISHES EXCEPT WHERE OTHERWISE STATED
 4. ALL DIMENSIONS TO BE PRESERVE THROUGHOUT THE CONSTRUCTION PERIOD
 5. ALL DIMENSIONS TO BE PRESERVE THROUGHOUT THE CONSTRUCTION PERIOD

ULTIMATE CLIENT

Quantum

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LEAD CONSULTANT

X B D

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PROJECT

METROPOLITAN TOWER LAGOS, NIGERIA

DRAWING PHASE

DESIGN PHASE

DRAWING SERIES

REINFORCEMENT DRAWINGS

BUILDING TYPE

MULTI STORY RESIDENTIAL

SHEET TITLE

TYPICAL STAIRCASE TYPE 1 DETAILS (SHT 2 OF 3)

PROJECT NO.

MS205

DRAWING NO.

MTR/RS01

REVISION NO.	SCALE	DATE	DESIGNED	APPROVED
1	As indicated	15/11/22	Designer	Approver
2			Checked	Originator
3			Checked	Author
4			Checked	Author
5			Checked	Author
6			Checked	Author
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